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EU-LAC Partnership on justice and security

GUIDELINES FOR DEVELOPING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE STRATEGIES IN JUSTICE AND SECURITY

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INTRODUCTION

AI has rapidly been gaining attention since the advent of deep learning methods in the late 2000s. What started with advances in computer vision has revolutionized other fields such as audio and text processing, control software for complex systems and generative techniques. In parallel, the possibilities and challenges for the justice and security sector have also kept pace. Computer vision progress has enabled smart cameras which now support surveillance world-wide or can help enforce rules regarding smartphone usage in traffic.

At the same time, advances in assisted driving pose new forensic challenges and legal questions regarding who is responsible for what event during accidents. Also, criminal organizations happily make use of AI to make their enterprises more productive and their deviant security more effective. This shifts criminal activities and opens new intervention possibilities. The evolution of technology also requires an evolution in the justice and security sector. The basics of investigations have for instance changed drastically over the years as the notion of evidence became enhanced with fingerprinting, DNA evidence and finally digitized evidence. These changes required widespread and difficult transformations across the sector but have yielded great progress. Finally, there is always more work than what can be managed. For instance, a typical police organization must process millions of data points a year just for topics like child abuse, digitized crime, and fraud. The variety of tasks is also highly diverse. They range from investigations to physical and digital surveillance, to harm prevention, to

victim support, to raids and many more. With AI there is an opportunity to keep the justice and security sector productive and prevent it from drowning in a sea of data.

Keeping track of all these developments is not easy and dealing with AI consequences, both the good and the bad, requires a dedicated strategy. In the EL PACCTO 2.0 “Artificial Intelligence and Organized Crime” report¹ it was identified that the Latin-America and Caribbean (LAC) region requires a regional AI strategy for the justice and security sector. Meetings regarding this topic have revealed that the LAC region has a lot of diversity when it comes to digitization and available resources. What unifies the region is the rising tide of cybercrime which is increasingly transnational, organized and AI supported. The overall impression is that the short-term focus for many partners is to protect their citizens and critical infrastructures, rather than for instance boost their administrative throughput to deal with growing case backlogs. Building an AI strategy as a spin-off from fighting digitized criminal activities is a sensible route. Across the world many countries originated their AI activities in operational domains such as the fight against Child Sexual Abuse Materials or online scams. Such domains are digitized, involve already AI, are pressing concerns, also require IT skills, and typically have established international collaborations.

Still, having a starting point is different from having a strategy. It can be hard to discuss an AI strategy because of the complex web of interdependencies. Experienced readers may recognize meetings regarding AI moving into detailed legislative discussions, discussions about IT infrastructure,

discussions about specific AI such as deep fakes generators, public versus private cloud debates or discussions about data management. Well-known AI examples such as Large Language Models (LLMs) and predictive policing can also distract from other AI opportunities. The aim of this document is help identify the broader considerations for building an AI strategy, components of a strategy and provide examples of specific elements. Where possible we highlight LAC and justice and security specific considerations.

Our approach is to first divide concerns and opportunities into ‘Dealing with AI and its consequences’ and ‘Utilizing AI’. Our aim with this divide is to provide a birds-eye view from which focus areas can be identified. Next, we shall discuss various strategic enablers that are needed to implement an AI strategy, or which themselves can be initial focus points. Finally, we shall discuss various components into which an AI strategy can be divided and a path forward for realizing the strategy.

BACKGROUND AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

Although the justice and security sector is in many regards similar to other governmental sectors, it also has unique aspects. In this guidelines document we aim to focus mostly on what makes the sector unique. In this section we discuss related documents that can contextualize and inspire AI strategies for the LAC region. Some of them also include overlapping sections of these guidelines in more details and with examples from similar domains.

EL PACCTO’s 2024 report on AI and organized crime² has served as the foundation for this report. The EL PACCTO report provides an excellent overview on a wide range of topics such as relevant legislation and strategic works, ethics and principles and examples how AI is used by criminals and the justice and security institutions. In this report we expand upon the examples and list them in a structured manner to help identify core challenges and applications to focus on for an AI strategy.

During the EL PACCTO meetings, a significant concern was voiced by LAC countries regarding the need for AI legislation. An up-to-date legal framework is needed to deal with new judicial and security challenges that AI imposes. To address this, any AI strategy for the justice and security sector must prioritize the development of comprehensive legislative frameworks that cover topics such as A) the criminalization of malicious uses of AI, B) review existing data protection to ensure it is robust with respects to new AI developments such as deep fake technology, C) clarify legal questions such as whether the use of AI tools can be an aggravating factor in crimes and D) harmonize legislation with regional

¹ Cristos Velasco, Jean Garcia Periche, Juan De Dios Gómez, Miguel Bueno Benedí (2024). *Artificial Intelligence and Organized Crime*. EL PACCTO 2.0 programme. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17076986>

² Cristos Velasco, Jean Garcia Periche, Juan De Dios Gómez, Miguel Bueno Benedí (2024). *Artificial Intelligence and Organized Crime*. EL PACCTO 2.0 programme. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17076986>

partners to ensure a consistent legal response and foster collaboration in transnational cases.

This report has very limited advice on legislation as it was mostly written from a technical perspective and is also accompanied by a sister EL PACCTO report that specifically addresses the legislative questions³. That report analyzes key trends in AI applications within the justice and security sector and the associated crimes. It also examines current legislation in the nine member countries of the Forum of Presidents of Legislative Branches of Central America and the Caribbean Basin (FOPREL). The report's aim is to provide a foundation for advancing the harmonized criminalization of offences that are facilitated, committed or complicated by AI tools.

The United Nations Institute for Disarmament Research UNIDIR released a policy brief in October 2024 with guidelines for developing a national AI strategy for the security and defence sector⁴. The report does not target any geographical region in particular. Like this document, the guidelines are not to prescribe a strategy but to provide handholds for creating one. Though the intersection of justice and security is not the same as security and defence, the report still applies mostly to the justice sector as well. It is therefore strongly recommended to read the document as extra background literature. In particular, the list of concrete aspects to consider for a strategy (our Strategy Component section, chapter 7) is more exhaustive in UNIDIR's report.

3 Reina Tortosa, Marc and Breyne, Emilie (2025) *Informe Técnico Legislativo Sobre la Tipificación Armonizada de Delitos Cometidos Mediante Sistemas y Herramientas de Inteligencia Artificial*. EL PACCTO 2.0.

4 Afina, Yasmin. October 2024. "Draft Guidelines for the Development of a National Strategy on AI in Security and Defence" by UNIDIR.

The Inter-American Development Bank (IDB) also regularly publishes relevant AI reports for the Latin-American and Caribbean region such as their report on AI for social good⁵ and their AI framework⁶. These reports are tailored towards the LAC region but do not address directly the justice and security sector. However, they provide good overviews on national level considerations. We do note that their scope tends to be much more oriented towards state-of-the-art AI that needs PhD level research and high performance compute, where in this report much attention is devoted to smaller AI endeavors which can be realized in a short time span.

In the judicial domain there are many reports that discuss the intersection between AI and legal concerns. For instance the Global Toolkit on AI and the rule of law for the Judiciary from UNESCO⁷ addresses a wide range of topics such as AI use-cases in the judiciary (including LAC examples), ethical challenges and human rights concerns regarding AI. The EU also releases public documents to help develop ethical thinking (such as the ethical charter for the judicial domain⁸) and overviews on AI usage in the judiciary⁹. Though originating from Europe, they tend to cover global geographical regions. Such documents are excellent materials for contextualizing AI discussions and a deeper dive than this document when it comes to ethics, legislative concerns and judicial considerations.

5 Gómez Mont, Constanza; Del Pozo, Claudia May; Martínez Pinto, Cristina; Martín del Campo Alcocer, Ana Victoria. (2020) *Artificial Intelligence for Social Good in Latin America and the Caribbean: The Regional landscape and 12 Country Snapshots*. IADB.org
6 Vargas, Fernando; Muenste, Arturo (2025). *Artificial Intelligence Framework for the Inter-American Development Group*. IADB.org
7 Stankovich, Miriam, Feldfeber, Ivana, Quiroga, Yasmin, Ciolfi Felice, Marianela, Marivate, Vukosi. (2023) *Global AI toolkit on AI and the rule of law for the judiciary*. UNESCO

8 European Commission for the efficiency of justice (CEPEJ). (2018) *European Ethical Charter on the Use of Artificial Intelligence in Judicial Systems and their environment*. Council of Europe.

9 CEPEJ (2025) *First AIAB Report on the Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the Judiciary. Based on the Information Contained in the Resource Center on Cyberjustice and AI*. Council of Europe.

Finally, it is insightful to look at AI-adjacent fields and lessons learned from there. In particular, the cybersecurity domain is relevant as it has many parallels with AI. Consider the following:

- Cybersecurity as a major concern in the justice and security sector is a relatively recent development that was related to technology disruption (especially the global adoption of the internet). For AI it is similarly the case that it is a recent development due to technology disruption (improved machine learning through better use of GPU and data).
- Cybersecurity has a strong separation between the adoption of cybersecurity technology (such as firewalls and malware scanners) and dealing with breaches of cybersecurity (new forms of crime, mostly cybercrime). For AI we also have to consider the use of AI tools by the justice and security sector (for instance customized legal search) and dealing with new forms of crime due to AI (such as deep fakes and data poisoning). We shall discuss these aspects at length in the next chapter.
- Cybersecurity and AI both have a strong data protection component. For cybersecurity it relates to protecting data from unauthorized access,

manipulation or destruction. For AI it relates to lawful and ethical use of data.

- Both cybersecurity and AI require specialized technical and legal expertise. Many countries still struggle to this day to accommodate these experts within their justice and security sector. For cybersecurity there is a strong private market with which government has to compete for talent. For AI it is similarly challenging to find and retain expertise.
- Cybersecurity and AI are high-velocity fields with new developments on a daily basis.
- National strategies for digital transformation and technology investments heavily impact what is attainable for justice and security sector for both cybersecurity and AI.

Because of these parallels and the fact that cybersecurity has been receiving attention for longer than AI, it is advised to consult reports such as the overview from the Organization of American States¹⁰. This overview covers the LAC region and has many practical guidelines that are also reflected in this report.

10 Almagro, Luis and Kaspar, Lea (2022) *National Cybersecurity Strategies: Lessons Learned and Reflections from the Americas and Other Regions*. Organization of American States. Global Partners Digital.

HOW TO USE AND READ THIS DOCUMENT

This guide encourages an iterative and pragmatic approach. The following steps are suggested to guide the process for creating a regional AI strategy for the justice and security sector:

Step 1: Understand and contextualize AI concerns (Sessions 1 & 2 - or more as needed)

Organize one or more sessions to thoroughly discuss the “Overview of AI Topics”.

During these sessions, critically assess if there are any additional, institution/country-specific concerns or nuances that are not adequately covered in this document. Adjust and expand the list of concerns as necessary to reflect the unique national context at hand.

Step 2: Identify coherent activity clusters (Session 3 - or more as needed)

Based on the comprehensive list of concerns, identify combinations of concerns that, when addressed together, would form coherent, multi-disciplinary activities.

The goal here is to define practical, multi-disciplinary projects that tackle specific sets of concerns. This avoids a situation where for instance operational experts, legal experts and technicians are doing what they find important but are not supporting each other.

Step 3: Assess strategic resources (Session 4 - or more as needed)

Discuss the “Strategic Enablers” in detail.

For each resource category (compute, talent, data, legislation, budget, ecosystems, existing domains), identify what is currently available within the justice and security sector.

Simultaneously, identify where extra development or acquisition of new resources is needed.

Critically review the coherent activity clusters identified in Step 2. Based on the resource analysis, it might be necessary to reconsider, refine, or even scale back certain initiatives if current resources are insufficient or development would be too challenging in the short to medium term. Prioritize what is achievable.

Step 4: Develop strategy components (separate working groups)

Once there is a clear understanding of the concerns, prioritized activity clusters, and assessed resources, begin working on the “Elements of an AI Strategy.”

Focus on producing concrete deliverables for each element, such as a vision document, a communication strategy, or an R&D roadmap.

Crucially, the emphasis is on getting started and making tangible progress. An iterative approach, with continuous learning and adaptation, is likely the most effective. The strategy should be a living document that evolves as the strategy is being realized.

AN OVERVIEW OF AI TOPICS

This document is geared towards facilitating focused discussions and bootstrapping the development of AI capabilities within the justice and security sector. One of the issues with formulating AI strategies is that there is an overwhelming number of topics that are on peoples' mind. The result can be sessions where at the end a list of concerns is voiced but little progress is made towards a strategy. It is impossible to formulate a single strategy that will solve everything at once. Therefore, in this chapter we will structure the various concerns so that later strategic synergies can be found when addressing combinations of these concerns. A high-level vision combined with real world metrics must inform these chosen combinations.

As a first split we divide topics in 'Consequences of AI' and 'Utilizing AI' to separate our thinking into risks and opportunities.

CONSEQUENCES OF AI

There are two broad categories of negative AI consequences that require strategic consideration. It makes sense that illicit AI practices are a primary concern as the justice and security sector is uniquely responsible for law-enforcement and protection. However, since the sector also holds a monopoly on violence and has far-reaching powers over citizens, it is not to be underestimated what institutional risks society is exposed to by the widespread adoption of AI. Within these concerns we can further drill down to common themes. Table 1 provides an overview of these themes and examples of them, which we shall discuss in the remainder of this section.

Figure 1 – Depicts the four-step process presented in this document, and the corresponding sections one can reference when developing and refining their own AI strategy

ABUSE OF AI	INSTITUTIONAL RISKS
Fake content <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Deep nudes ● Spear phishing ● Scams 	Bad data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Diversity ● Impact of past choices ● Digitization deficiencies ● Data quality
AI sabotage <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data poisoning ● Copyright & IP ● Leaked models 	Transparency <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Responsibility gaps ● Fair treatment – explainability ● Public trust, chilling effects
Autonomous functions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● New forensics questions ● Drones ● Agentic AI 	Data protection <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Illegitimate use by civil servants ● Information leaks to clouds
Deviant AI utilization <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lower barrier to entry ● Pattern obfuscation ● Victim scanning 	Public-private tensions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Vendor lock-ins ● Sovereignty ● Malinvestments ● Energy dependency
	Data overload <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Deep fakes in evidence ● Agents pushing complaints ● Legal DDoS
	Overuse <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sustainability ● Loss of skills
	Knowledge gaps <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Digital skills ● AI literacy

Table 1 Overview of topics regarding AI and its consequences

ABUSE OF AI

The most visible issue to address for the justice and security sector is abuse and illicit use of AI. New crime forms include crime conducted with AI and against AI itself, and autonomous functionalities raise new questions regarding blame and responsibility. Overall productivity increases of certain criminal enterprises also make perpetrators move from one activity to another. All these developments cause shifts in workloads and the nature of work to be done across the sector.

Fake content

One the most impact new AI developments has been generative AI. The ability to quickly generate text, video and audio has enabled new forms of crime and enhanced pre-existing ones. For instance, (spear) phishing and digitized fraud schemes are significantly easier if AI can generate

personalized messages towards victims based on data that it can find online. Voice cloning is also on the rise in ‘CEO scams’ and ‘WhatsApp/friend-in-need scams’. A five second audio fragment from a TikTok is all it takes nowadays to clone a voice. Especially in the LAC region it is common to conduct business via channels a such as WhatsApp, which makes this region particularly vulnerable for this type of crime.

New forms of crime are also introduced. Deep nudes are a phenomenon where imagery of people is converted into pornographic material. Though reports vary, the estimates are that over 95% of such deep nudes is a form of technology-assisted gender-based violence against women. They can be a component of for instance harassment and extortion. The fact that many minors create and share such pictures among each other is also a growing concern.

Strategic considerations.

As part of the EL PACCTO meetings it has been mentioned multiple times that deep fakes, fraud and cybercrime in general are major challenges for the LAC region. Vulnerabilities lie in unequal digital literacy among civilians which makes that they often do not understand their rights and protective measures. Also, critical infrastructures are more vulnerable in some countries than others, which makes the impact of ransomware much higher. Many countries also struggle with legislating AI supported or committed crime. Finally, in organized crime there is an increasing trend where digitized crime is used to finance other illicit operations such as subversive crime and terrorism. As digitized crime is typically cross-border, it poses also additional pressure on international collaboration.

AI sabotage

AI itself can also be the target of undesirable activities. AI sabotage, which encompasses topics such as data poisoning and harmful prompt injection, can negatively affect the integrity and reliability of AI systems. For instance: LLM instructions or source documents can be subtly modified in such a way that interpretations of textual evidence in investigations or summaries of interrogations are negatively affected, thus poisoning whole legal processes. The problem becomes particularly pressing if the required data is to be procured from sources outside of the zone-of-control of the sector, such as open-source repositories from abroad.

A related AI-specific issue is the question of knowledge distillation and copyright. Distillation techniques allow for training a smaller or similar models based on outputs of another model. If the 'teacher' model

is trained on protected data, then it is often unclear what the legal rules are with respect to training the 'students' model. In addition, cyber-attacks often aim to gain special knowledge and from models there might be valuable information extracted with inference attacks. When a model is stolen that was trained or finetuned with government data, how bad is that situation compared to a direct leak of the training data?

For the near future we can expect more developments in the field of agentic AI. Although the concept of agents is not new, their realization via the integration LLMs with each other and external tools and given this field a new boost. The idea of agentic AI is that it allows for more autonomous functionalities within the digital domain. If companies move to agentic AI for core processes, then this will enable a new host of attack opportunities. For instance, how must the justice sector react when someone is purposefully manipulating an agentic AI to cause costs or harm, or jailbreaks it for some monetary benefit like a promised service? How much responsibility to avoid jailbreaking lies at the deployer's side and how much protection do users get by relying on the output of agents?

Strategic considerations.

A strategy that relies on maximally utilizing open-source data and procurement should include extensive safeguards against AI sabotage by external actors. A strategy that focuses on data sovereignty and local development would have less emphasis on this factor but more with regards to what can be leaked from their models if they are stolen. However, for the wider economic activity of a country it may still be required to properly legislate AI sabotage to protect local industries. Also, copyright

interpretations may need to be revised to deal with questions regarding knowledge distillation.

Autonomous functionalities

Autonomous vehicles as we know them today have been in development since the late seventies. And although general availability of true autonomous vehicles is still not achieved, there are increasingly more driverless vehicles deployed across the world as for instance taxi services. Regardless of true autonomy, assisted and telemetry-based driving is widely available and poses related challenges. There are two main impacts of AI in vehicle control. The first is to determine the responsibility of for instance an accident. Past cases have led to a lot of discussion around who is responsible for an accident when the driver and the vehicle are together driving, rather than just the driver. Similarly, for agentic AI there must be a framework to assign responsibility for when things go wrong. Adjacent to the AI sabotage discussion it must be considered that an autonomous functionality can also be designed or manipulated to cause harm.

Organized crime can also make use of autonomous functionalities. In contrast to governments, they are not limiting themselves with respect to autonomous weapons or 'loitering munition'. Especially drone use is on the rise for drug transport, reconnaissance and bombing missions. Autonomy aspects might lead to new counter measure opportunities for such applications of drones.

Strategic considerations.

For countries with no widespread adoption of autonomous functionalities it might be less pressing to include the related consequences explicitly in a strategy.

However, for those that do have to deal with the issue it would be natural to see it as extensions of cybersecurity and in general dealing with new forms of digitized evidence.

Deviant AI utilization

Unfortunately, all the opportunity that the AI field offers for the justice and security sector is similarly helpful for criminal enterprises. For example, the extensive knowledge that LLM's make accessible also includes knowledge on how to commit crime. Some developments have even been the production of Dark LLMs which specifically allow users to create malware, thus lowering the barrier to entry for cybercrime. In general AI can be used to scale up criminal processes, including automating conversations with victims, finding vulnerable people via open-source information and bought datasets or writing social engineering scripts. AI can also help with obfuscation such as scrambling transactions to avoid patterns to emerge that law-enforcement can pick up.

Strategic considerations.

When we consider deviant AI there is usually not per se much that can be done in terms of criminalizing certain uses. Rather, it should inform us about future trends. Crime that becomes easier to commit at a large scale will increase in size and reduce alternative types of crime. This has likely contributed in various countries to a decline in physical crime such as burglary and an increase in online scams. As a result, the justice and security sector should take appropriate steps to reorganize in order to prepare for these shifting workloads.

INSTITUTIONAL RISKS

Although the use of AI by criminals rightfully gets a lot of attention, it is certainly not the only aspect of AI that poses risks to a safe society. The algorithmization of governments leads to concerns regarding fair and transparent decision making. Past cases of mishandling of technology such as the Dutch benefits scandal, which has wrecked many lives, prove that these are valid concerns. The well-known COMPAS case highlighted how proprietary usage of AI by governments, even when using small decision-rule based algorithms with few features, can lead to biased decisions by government institutions. Additionally, governments across the world aim for state-of-the-art digitized systems which conflict with sustainability goals. Both within the LAC region and the EU many resources are directed to guidelines,

research, and legislation for steering the adoption of AI towards responsible practices.

Bad data

A core resource for governments and in particular AI development is data. The origin of this data varies from civil servants entering and processing it, to reports by civilians and private institutes, to international input, open-source intelligence, and confiscated data carriers. All this data must be structured and processed to make it accessible. This is a laborious process that involves a lot of human effort.

It is often considered that structured data is trustworthy enough to directly use for AI tools, but in reality, *most data that is found in the justice and security sector is not good*

enough. Across the world, interactions with data scientists from the sector reveal that one of the most common projects is to reclassify incidents based on their textual description. Officers interchange semantically close incident codes like ‘harassment’ and ‘stalking’, or simply pick the first option in a dropdown menu if multiple options could apply. The result is that changes in the order of codes in a form suddenly impact crime statistics. On the AI side there is a danger that tools are simply not performing well due to the lack of quality data.

Undesirable bias is to be expected in any data source and proper risk management should address the potential negative side effects and encourage mitigation measures. Particular bias induced harm includes over-policing or under-serving parts of the population, discrimination, unfair treatment and exacerbating societal inequalities.

From experience, we can also share that there is a general overestimation of the predictive value of data within the sector. A lot of science fiction suggests that with sufficient data anything is predictable. This has led to many police organizations embracing predictive policing tools, or justice institutes using prediction algorithms to determine recidivism. However, many data science teams have seen that their data just isn’t predictive beyond average statistics. Reasons can be that the underlying phenomenon changes too quick before a pattern can be established, that relevant factors cannot be measured or that there is inherent noise.

Strategic considerations.

The data environment within the sector should have its own dedicated strategy.

An AI strategy should work with the constraints that result from the data environment and focus on at least not exacerbating problems. For the production of high-quality data it can be considered to create a dedicated facility to process and enrich data specifically for AI usage.

Transparency

Many AI systems rely on black-box approaches. These black boxes make it hard or impossible to exactly discern the route from input data to outcome. This can be problematic for governments that aim to be transparent about their choices. For instance, in the common example of predictive policing it might be the case that questions are raised regarding the allocation of resources. If these are allocated via a black-box prediction model, then it is not possible to properly defend these decisions. In turn, this can lead to diminishing public trust and hinders the ability to correct errors or unwanted biases.

An additional issue might be that AI creates confusion regarding responsibility – known as responsibility gaps. When an agentic AI causes harm, who is to blame? The developer, the human operator that relied on its output? Current legislative frameworks typically struggle with assigning responsibility in the context of autonomous functionalities.

Aside from the transparency of AI itself, one can also consider transparency in the sense of how open the sector is about the use of AI. Across the world various countries now work on public algorithm registers to communicate openly about how algorithms impact the lives of citizens. The reason for such transparency is to allow for accountability, but also to diminish

phenomena such as the chilling effect.¹¹ Research among XR demonstrators has for instance shown that civilians delete their social media in fear of being profiled by law-enforcement¹².

Strategic considerations.

Fostering public trust should play a significant role in any AI strategy. As such, it should always be considered whether transparent methods can be chosen in favor of black boxes, and whether the use of AI can always be explained well towards society.

Data protection

AI also increases the risk of information leaks in various ways. Most countries operate under strict public cloud strategies which do not allow operational data to be sent to the cloud. However, personnel can still avoid these policies by using their own private accounts for websites like DeepSeek and OpenAI. This becomes especially more pressing as people start using more of these tools at home or during their education. If there is not a local and safe facility available, one risks leaking information this way.

Strategic considerations.

Personnel should be made aware of the risks that data leaks impose. Policy regarding the use of external tools should be communicated clearly. For sovereignty-oriented strategies it would be wise to invest in hosting local versions of LLM's in national or private clouds. Not using large

¹¹ The chilling effect refers to the phenomenon where someone inhibits exercising their legitimate natural or legal rights because they fear potential negative consequences. This is often induced by being monitored and is known to be enhanced by AI application in surveillance.

¹² Storbeck, M., Jacobs, G., Schuilenburg, M., & van den Akker, R. (2025). Surveillance experiences of extinction rebellion activists and police: Unpacking the technologization of Dutch protest policing. *Big Data & Society*, 12(1)

scale datacenters will impact the possible ambitions of an AI strategy.

Public-private tensions

The increasing reliance on private sector AI solutions by justice and security sectors presents a complex problem: a tension between public good and private interests. Public entities often lack the in-house expertise and infrastructure for advanced AI development and thus rely on private vendors. This creates a significant risk of vendor lock-in, where agencies become overly dependent on a single provider's proprietary systems, making it costly and difficult to switch to alternative solutions. This limits flexibility and shifts control over critical public functions to private companies. Consequently, it becomes challenging for public oversight bodies to ensure fairness, transparency, and adherence to all relevant legal rules.

For smaller entities in the LAC region this may also more heavily impact sovereignty concerns. Without a local AI industry, one has to procure solutions from abroad. There is also the risk that AI models developed elsewhere may not adequately reflect local socioeconomic, linguistic, and cultural realities, leading to biased or ineffective outcomes in judicial processes or security operations.

Malinvestments due to false or exaggerated claims from AI vendors can lead to the adoption of ineffective or even harmful technologies, diverting scarce public funds from more appropriate solutions and causing missed opportunity costs. This does not just limit itself to private vendors. Public information may also misinform internal development choices. It is always important to determine how the impact of a new AI solution will be measured.

Strategic considerations.

The public-private tensions should be addressed in any AI strategy as it has a major impact on the rest of the strategy such as choices regarding in-house expertise. For in-house oriented AI strategies it is required to have the appropriate development environments and eventually AI maintenance expertise such as MLOps. For private-industry oriented strategies it particularly necessitates robust procurement frameworks that emphasize interoperability, data portability, and open standards to prevent vendor lock-in. Regardless of the main direction, the sector should work on evaluation frameworks to determine which AI modules actually provide value.

Data overload

Big data challenges were already faced by the justice and security sector, but AI usage across society exacerbates the problem. For instance, civilians can use AI to automatically fight traffic tickets or file complaints, companies can use AI to transcribe meetings and image generation can increase CSAM flows. All these kinds of activities increase the overall digital footprint that the security and justice sector has to deal with during regular administrative tasks and investigations. It is humanly impossible to look at all the data and therefore heavy filtering, including AI-driven filters, becomes necessary.

A second aspect relates more to overall digitization. For instance, to support autonomous functionalities it is required to outfit a vehicle with sensors and compute. These have a digital footprint that can be essential for an investigation. For instance, drive seat sensor readings may show behavioral patterns that can determine who was operating a vehicle at some point. Smartwatches may provide

key information regarding when someone was still alive. To extract and use this data it is often required to have specialized knowledge regarding digital forensics and data analytics.

Strategic considerations.

Focusing on productivity gains within an AI strategy is not optional. The sector needs a thorough understanding about how data is filtered, and which role AI can play in that. The need for new forensics expertise may depend more on the overall state of adoption of new devices within a society. Given the rise of AI abuse in scams it will also be necessary to address

understanding of manipulated/generated content within legal processes and reconsidering admissibility of AI generated content in court.

Overuse

More and more studies show that the use of AI can lower skill levels such as reading, writing and critical thinking. Within the justice and security sector this can lead to critical decisions seemingly being made by (meaningful) humans in the loop, but in reality, completely originating from AI. When such AI is in addition not transparent it can further damage sound legal processes. This loss of skills can also

skew evaluation results. Where a user may be able to correct an AI's mistake initially, over time this capability may diminish, leading to an overall skills stagnation in the sector.

Another aspect is the considerable cost of energy and hardware that comes with advanced AI systems. LLMs are now a go-to solution for many tasks which can also be solved with simpler and more efficient techniques. The energy usage of AI increases rapidly. Private companies are planning to construct nuclear powerplants to keep up with the energy demand. This is energy that could be used to replace fossil fuels. Hence, the widespread adoption of advanced AI goes against the sustainability goals that most countries have. Per individual query, especially for text applications, the cost is not prohibitive. But to fully process for instance all confiscated data and OSINT data through expensive GPU's can add up over time.

Strategic considerations.

A common pitfall is to put 'state of the art technology' central in a strategy. This incentivizes employees to reach for the most advanced, expensive, and often untested AI solutions. It is better to put core problems central and from there determine which promising AI technologies are to be investigated as potential solutions.

Knowledge gaps

A lack of knowledge can lead to serious damage and disinvestment. On the user side there are examples of lawyers and researchers that blindly submit documents with hallucinated sources. Potential victims can be extra vulnerable for AI driven crime if they are not knowledgeable about modern capabilities. And management can

hopelessly waste resources on AI projects that go nowhere or turn out to break ethical guidelines or legal constraints.

Many countries already struggle with digitization skills, and AI risks make these struggles even more urgent. Especially for users of systems some kind of baseline is needed in understanding the capabilities and limitations of AI so that over-reliance is avoided regarding what people see on their screen. In particular, for the justice and security sector there should also be training on spotting or compensating for AI bias, how to write down conclusions where AI played a role in the reasoning process, what rules systems need to comply with and how AI systems are evaluated and validated.

Strategic considerations.

The justice and security sector is not positioned well to increase digital skills or AI literacy across the wider population. However, as part of an AI strategy it can endeavor to help for instance the education sector to raise awareness and provide reasons for focusing more on the topic. Within the justice and security sector, and as part of legislation, certain base lines of AI literacy can be made mandatory before AI systems are allowed to be deployed.

UTILIZING AI

The justice and security sector as a broad range of unique AI applications. These include decision support for judges, recidivism prediction and predictive policing. However, there are also many other ways in which AI can support the sector. Broadly speaking, projects are either aimed at dealing with capacity issues, i.e., increasing productivity, or creating new ways of working for innovation or quality purposes. Table two provides an initial overview of directions that can be focused on, and the rest of this section will provide more details on the specifics.

PRODUCTIVITY	INNOVATION AND QUALITY
Triage <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Case backlogs ● Intervention options 	Consistency <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Bias mitigation ● Case based reasoning ● Knowledge distribution
Administration <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Transcription ● Summarization ● Data-entry 	Data quality <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data entry enhancement ● Digitization
Self-help <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Internal/external helpdesks ● Knowledge management 	Optimization <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Business process analysis ● Inter-institutional waste
Data to information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Search ● Analytics ● Data federation 	New capabilities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fugitive interception ● Infiltrating online spaces ● Deviant AI disruptions ● Equal access to tools
Automation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● RPA ● Agentic AI 	

Table 2 Overview of topics regarding utilizing AI

PRODUCTIVITY

The promises of productivity gain through AI applications have been a driving force behind the interest in AI. This aligns with the massive challenges the justice and security sector has, where productivity gains could free up precious human time. From focusing on promising leads, to self-help and automation; there are many ways in which the sector can make use of AI.

Triage

It is a given that the justice and security sector will always have more work than can be handled. LAC countries with high murder rates deal, for instance, with large case backlogs and the rise of cybercrime leads to thousands of extra cases. Complex cases against organized crime are also rich in data. Investigators must sift through police reports, witness statements, forensic analyses, financial transactions,

digital communications and much more. Other issues include for instance a large presence of remote areas or shortages of personnel, which makes it difficult to maintain a continuous physical presence. One of the core tasks of the sector is hence to perform some type of triage to determine where resources are spent building cases, following up on reports, spend time in the public (e.g. surveillance), etc.

The triage process can feel often arbitrary and at the same time high stakes. A case that ends nowhere can constitute a huge loss of resources. AI models can rapidly process and analyze datasets, identifying relevant patterns, anomalies, and connections that might be imperceptible to human eyes. For example, in managing case backlogs, AI can prioritize cases based on their urgency, complexity, or potential for swift resolution, flagging those that require immediate human attention and reading through to determine what's critical and what's irrelevant. This means that judges, prosecutors, and investigators are presented with a distilled overview of the most pertinent facts, and thus avoiding the need to manually review the bulk of documents. Similarly, in disrupting criminal networks, AI can analyze communication patterns, financial transactions, and geographical data to map out network structures, identify key actors, and in some cases predict future criminal activities. By analyzing data from various sources, AI can pinpoint suspicious activities and highlight intelligence that leads to effective interventions, allowing law enforcement to act decisively against illicit operations, rather than being bogged down in information overload.

Strategic considerations.

To create AI applications that help allocate

resources it is important to first have a strategic choice on which domain struggle in their triage processes and secondly to have the data available that enables the triage in the first place. AI supported triage builds on other AI developments for human operators like search and analytics. If such functionalities are not present, then it is better to first focus on realizing those.

Administration

The justice and security sector is burdened by significant administrative overhead. The overhead is, for a large part, there for good reasons. Sound legal processes require careful logging of what exactly was done during investigations at any point. The administrative process is also the main source of data for most AI developments within the sector. High-quality data entry is therefore crucial for any AI strategy.

Ideally most of the data would be nicely 'structured' via extensive forms that avoid free text. It is not only impossible to capture the complexity of the sector in forms, but it is also a highly negative experience for the person filling in the form to go through massive fields of options. The sector therefore has a gigantic volume of unstructured data—from witness statements and court transcripts to investigative reports and evidence logs. Officers, investigators and other personnel that must deal with these forms often cite it as a chore, taking away the enjoyment of their work and preventing them from doing their 'real' job.

AI offers many opportunities to address this problem by automating and augmenting these labor-intensive administrative tasks. Summarization tools, for instance, can rapidly condense lengthy legal documents, police reports, or witness testimonies into concise overviews, allowing investigators

and legal professionals to get to the key information. Transcription software can convert audio and video recordings of interviews, interrogations, and court proceedings into accurate text, drastically reducing the time and cost associated with manual transcription and ensuring a searchable record. Similarly, AI-powered data-entry systems can automate the extraction and input of information from various documents into structured databases, minimizing human error and accelerating the processing of case files, evidence, and administrative paperwork. By handling these repetitive, high-volume tasks, AI frees up human experts to focus on complex analysis, strategic decision-making, and direct citizen engagement.

Strategic considerations.

The administrative domain benefits the most from natural language processing. Though there are many smaller AI techniques that can already alleviate a lot of pressure, for the mid to long-term the most promising developments in this field lie in the application of LLMs. A focus on the administrative would therefore naturally entail a focus on such AI techniques as well.

Self-help

There have been major labor shifts in industries such as the banking sector by enabling customers to help themselves. For the justice and security sector it could

similarly reduce workloads if for certain types of crimes victims can file themselves reports instead of having to go to a police bureau. This also includes self-help for within the justice and security sector. One of the core challenges is to convey the right personalized knowledge and information to the user which enables them to solve their problem or file a request in a manner that is easy to process later.

The support of users in self-help environments is exactly where AI can shine. AI-powered chatbots, virtual assistants, and online platforms can be deployed to provide instant, 24/7 access to information regarding legal procedures, common rights, frequently asked questions about security protocols, and guide citizens through initial stages of reporting minor incidents or filing basic complaints. This allows human personnel to focus on complex requests that may require human judgment and empathy or fall out of scope for the self-help environment.

Strategic considerations.

This shift towards AI-enabled self-help may first require policy changes such as the admissibility of digitally signed victim reports. It is also a kind of change that requires a careful redesign of business processes so that human 'life-lines' remain available and that civilians with low literacy skills or limited access to digital portals are not excluded.

Data to information

The justice and security sector collects and produces an overwhelming volume of raw data, ranging from police reports, surveillance footage and forensic evidence to judicial records, financial transactions and social media interactions. Human analysts are simply unable to process and connect the dots across such vast and varied datasets, leading to missed patterns, delayed responses, and resource inefficiencies. Also ambitions regarding

data-driven policing are severely hampered if the raw data cannot be transformed into insight, which can hinder evidence-based policymaking and strategic planning within the sector.

The transformation from all this raw data to actionable insight is often referred to as data analytics. AI plays a supportive role in this field by ways of processing the unstructured data parts, enabling search methods and detecting anomalies. Since the sector has such heterogeneous data, it can also help to look at AI techniques for federating data sources. An example is for instance tracking entities across different types of datasets (e.g. a container with drugs can be tracked through communication about that container, port logs, logs from logistics companies, etc.). It should be noted though that data analytics is considered its own field. Topics such as visualization, (advanced) statistics and business intelligence lie at the core of it.

Strategic considerations.

A strategic focus on analytics is a good starting point and creates a natural launch pad for further AI developments. The basics for analytics also overlap with the basics of many AI tools such as data availability and the legality of using operational data in new ways. Statistical skills that are required for data analytics are also required for addressing concerns such as bias detection and mitigation.

Automation

So far we've discussed AI applications that focus on enhancing and supporting humans. For less risky and especially routine activities it is even more productive to fully automate these tasks. This frees human personnel from mundane tasks,

allowing them to focus on more complex, strategic work requiring human judgment and creativity.

There are various approaches to automation that have varying degrees of AI in them. A common first step is to start with Robotic Process Automation. RPA can automate repetitive, rule-based tasks such as data entry from claim forms, document generation, and the compilation of routine reports. RPA tools often require no AI at all and simply simulate mouse clicks and key hits. Good use-cases include the transfer of data from one system to another which is commonly done manually within the sector. For instance, in Caribbean judiciaries, RPA tools are already proving valuable in streamlining court administration and improving case management.

Agentic AI goes beyond rigid rule-following. It can interpret context, make autonomous decisions, and adapt to changing environments to achieve specific goals. In the justice and security domain, agentic AI could decide by itself which sources to query under what circumstances, thus automating more advanced processes to determine whether for instance an individual occurs in various institution databases. Modern agentic AI solutions rely heavily on LLMs to deal with the large amount of unstructured natural text in the justice and security sector.

Strategic considerations.

A strategy that focus on automation needs to be particularly careful about meaningful humans in the loop and guardrails to ensure that automated systems keep operating as intended. There's also the danger of solidifying legacy software instead of updating it to modern solutions, because that would break the automation layer thus leading to more work initially.

Simple automation such as RPA could be a good way for quick wins. Agentic AI would rely on much more advanced digital infrastructures and a more mature framework on for instance the ethical side. The use of heavy AI like LLMs can be avoided in many cases if data is better structured.

INNOVATION AND QUALITY

Not all AI applications are geared towards productivity gains. Another major aspect of AI for the sector is that it allows for innovative new ways of working and improving the overall quality of institutions.

Consistency

It is especially important for the justice and security sector to maintain high levels of fairness and equality. This means that equal cases should consistently lead to equal outcomes. If decisions are made based on biased data or inconsistent application of legal frameworks, it undermines the foundation of justice. However, in day to day work it is hard to maintain consistency due to factors like bias, differences in expertise and unclear policy.

AI can play various roles in promoting fairness and equality. Specialized AI techniques can mitigate or compensate for systemic or human biases and case-based reasoning techniques can make users aware of similar past situations in order to establish relevant precedents. Aside from specific cases, knowledge management systems can help share expertise or work instructions in proactive manner. Retrieval Augmented Generation systems can for instance read and interpret a user's context and proactively notify them of relevant policy details or detect if instructions were not followed correctly.

Strategic considerations.

The topic of consistency fits well in strategies that focus on ethics and human centered AI. One does need to be aware of the risk that the influence of AI advice can lead to personnel operating on auto-pilot mode and not critically considering the AI output. Systems such as case-based reasoning and RAG also overlap for a large part with search functionalities.

Data quality

The problem of poor data quality, stemming from manual entry errors, inconsistencies, and fragmented information, significantly hampers efficiency and decision-making. The result within the justice and security sector can be particularly high impact. For instance, errors in police reports, witness statements, or forensic analyses can lead to miscarriages of justice, prolonged investigations, or even the release of dangerous individuals. The source of these problems varies from paper-driven procedures to poorly designed forms and data-entry interfaces.

AI can assist with data entry through intelligent autofill suggestions and real-time validation, thereby reducing human error. Beyond data capture, AI can detect anomalies and inconsistencies within datasets. This could inform users about where data might be entered incorrectly or highlighting errors in documents and procedures during investigations. Likewise, it can provide feedback on the clarity of policies, skill levels of personnel and the quality of work instructions by highlighting which processes produce low quality data.

Strategic considerations.

If poor data quality is a structural problem

then it would make sense to highly prioritize the topic in a strategy. After all, with poor quality there is likely also few opportunities for other AI applications. In such cases it is best to see AI as supportive to a digitization strategy. Data quality measures also go hand in hand with data entry automation for productivity gains, though they are not completely the same. Finding an inconsistency in a report is different than having speech to text and LLMs to quickly write the report.

Optimization

Typically, when data analytics and related fields are discussed within the justice and security sector it pertains to finding and investigating crime across data sources. However, one can apply the same assortment of techniques to find bottlenecks and irregularities within the sector itself. The number of efficiencies stemming from convoluted manual processes, information silos between institutions, and the waste of resources due to one institute rejecting the output of another can be overwhelming. Choosing where to even start improving the situation is not an easy task.

By employing AI for business process analyses, institutions can map and understand their workflows in detail, identifying bottlenecks, redundancies, and points of inter-institutional waste. Furthermore, predictive analytics can help identify patterns in case dismissals, allowing for proactive interventions to prevent cases from being thrown out due to administrative or procedural flaws. This can also extend to identifying potential biases in judicial processes or resource allocation, promoting greater fairness and transparency. As such, optimization activities overlap strongly with aims to increase productivity and consistency, with

the difference being that for optimization we are not per se talking about AI solutions to alleviate the identified bottlenecks and waste.

Strategic considerations.

A core focus on optimization within the justice and security sector can help to streamline process and support data-driven policy-making. The insights into the overall workings of the sector can also inform subsequent strategic choice on where to focus AI developments. The implementation of optimization suggestions is generally not a technical challenge, but more of a governance and change management challenge.

New capabilities

Just like AI allows for new ways of crime like AI sabotage, it also allows for new ways of law-enforcement, crime prevention and prosecution. Sometimes this will require rethinking processes that have evolved from paperwork and human labor to properly incorporate AI capabilities. For instance, a lot of communication between teams in the justice and security sector happens via e-mail and administrative systems with extensive text data. This is a natural result from digitizing the analogue situation of letters and written reports. If prosecutor offices and investigative teams use AI to automate processing input data such as data-entry and summarization, and then also use AI to formulate responses, then one can question the need for this text → data, data → text, text → data transformation. A new way of working where systems directly exchange information and verbalization to natural language only happens when required, could be much more efficient. This can have far reaching consequences such as rethinking basic notions such as signatures

and the chain of custody.

Other opportunities lie in taking advantage of the fact that AI for crime regularly concentrates on a few services such as image generation and LLMs, which at least for the moment cannot be run locally for convincing effects in many criminal use-cases. A disruption of those services, or way of monitoring them, can be a fruitful approach to disrupting various forms of scams and being able to find anonymous users of such services. Investigative teams can also themselves make use of deep fakes to infiltrate online spaces and maintain artificial online persona.

The applications do not just limit themselves to the digital domain. Advanced simulation-optimization techniques can help with positioning police vehicles during chases, smart cameras allow for enforcing laws related to smart phones in traffic and license plate recognition can track stolen vehicles. The list of possibilities is endless. Dedicated tech horizon scans, bottom-up innovation networks and international exchange of ideas can help identify good opportunities.

Strategic considerations.

A strategy with a strong focus on new capabilities benefits from having established research ecosystems in the nation. R&D processes take long which necessitates long-term planning and commitment and acceptance that some experiments fail. Having a new capability may give the sector an edge against for instance organized crime that continuously tries to obfuscate their activities based on their knowledge of how law-enforcement operates.

EXAMPLE SYNERGY TO LOOK FOR

Assume it is determined that the illicit AI use in scams with deep fakes and voice clones are a strategic operational priority to address (*AI and its consequences -> Illicit AI use -> fake content*). Since deep fakes are adjacent to computer vision and voice cloning is adjacent to speech to text, it is strategic to also direct productivity-oriented developments towards these topics. Examples would be OCR¹³ modules

¹³ Optical character recognition. This allows AI to get text from images. Good, dedicated OCR models exist or can be trained without the need of multi-modal LLM's.

for promoting digitization within the sector (*Utilizing AI -> innovation and quality -> data quality*) and speech to text to make audio in evidence searchable (*Utilizing AI -> productivity -> data to information and utilizing AI*). On the legislation side it is a good opportunity to address the concerns regarding validity of evidence in the face of generative AI (*AI and its consequences -> Institutional risks -> data overload*). This way addressing illicit AI use, institutional risks, productivity opportunities and innovative ways of working can be synergized. Since operational experts work on the scams, technical experts work on the underlying technology, legal experts deal with the legislative aspects, and IT architects work

on new data warehousing, the result is a coherent multi-disciplinary network of experts to address important concerns.

From here new directions can be sprouted. If the disciplines are not strategically aligned, then for instance the operational experts might work on scams – but they get stuck because they don't know how to deal with the generative AI. The technical experts could work on LLM's but they get stuck because it is unclear if LLM's are allowed to be used in an operational context. Legal experts work on data protection so they're too busy to help with dealing with fake data in evidence or LLM concerns. And IT architects are building a data lake without a strategy to use big data analytics. These are all sensible topics but you miss the synergy of experts being able to help each other.

It should be noted though that we do not advocate for ignoring all concerns except the prioritized ones. For each concern it should be investigated what *must* be done now and what can be done at a later point.

RISK ASSESSMENT¹⁴

The institutional risks column of Table 1 applies to most AI systems within the justice and security sector. Hence, whenever AI uses from Table 2 are picked as core activities, then some form of risk assessment is going to be needed. It is therefore recommended that any regional, national or institutional strategy AI strategy incorporates a risk analysis mechanism. This framework would allow for the classification of both AI tools and the activities in which they are deployed, based

¹⁴ This section is based on input that was provided by Argentine partners.

on their potential impact on fundamental rights, the specific institutional function involved, and the level of technological autonomy. A practical way to implement this is through a risk matrix, which would be developed by intersecting ethical principles with technical requirements. The matrix would be integrated with operational dimensions, such as the type of data processed, the sensitivity of the institutional function, the degree of system autonomy, the possibility of meaningful human oversight, the traceability of the process, and the reversibility of its effects.

Each category of risk could then be associated with proportional mitigation measures. These could include requirements for internal or external audits, reinforced human oversight, ex-ante impact assessments, detailed usage logs, purpose limits, and periodic review protocols. In this context, the risk classification model from the European Union's Artificial Intelligence Act serves as a useful and adaptable reference for the Latin American and Caribbean region. Its gradual approach—which distinguishes between prohibited, high-risk, limited-risk, and minimal-risk uses—provides a clear framework for establishing obligations that are proportional to the potential impact of each system, thereby guiding both regulatory and operational decisions. This approach is currently being applied in the Artificial Intelligence Program of the Public Prosecutor's Office of the Argentine Republic, where a risk analysis model is being developed to combine ethical principles, institutional functions, and technical requirements to ensure responsible AI implementation.

Furthermore, in a regional context characterized by structural budgetary constraints, it is crucial that the strategy includes clear criteria for the use of private

sector solutions. The level of risk identified through the proposed analysis and the type of institutional function involved should be primary considerations. For activities classified as low-risk, the use of pre-existing tools may be permitted, provided they meet minimum standards for security, data protection, and traceability. However, for highly sensitive or high-risk functions, the strategy should prioritize proprietary developments or solutions hosted in environments controlled by the institution itself. This approach ensures the safe and responsible management of technology, maintaining institutional integrity and public trust. In the appendices we address further concerns regarding the discussion around 'make-or-buy' analyses.

For the justice and security sector, a clear example of a high-risk AI system would be an AI system designed to assess the risk of a person re-offending after serving a criminal sentence. This tool analyzes various data points about the person's criminal history, social background, and other variables to provide a risk score to a parole board.

This AI system is classified as high-risk under the EU AI Act for two main reasons:

- It falls into a high-risk sector: The Act explicitly lists AI systems used in the administration of justice and law enforcement as a high-risk category because of the significant impact they can have on people's lives and liberty.
- It affects fundamental rights: A decision based on this tool could directly influence a person's freedom and their ability to reintegrate into society. A biased or inaccurate risk score could lead to the denial of parole, infringing upon their right to liberty and potentially perpetuating social

inequalities.

Because of this classification, the party that developed the system must demonstrate compliance with the Act's requirements before the system can be used. This includes showing that the training data is high-quality and unbiased, providing a detailed audit trail of the system's decisions, and ensuring that the AI's output is not the sole factor in the parole board's decision-making process. As most AI in the justice domain, the system must be used as a support tool for human judgment, not as a replacement for it.

Note that compliance documentation, audits and other forms of risk management increase AI projects' costs beyond what is typical for software development. When choosing activities to start with, it is therefore further recommended to choose 'safe' initial projects such as data entry support, visualization techniques and transcription tools.

FIVE FUNDAMENTAL CONCERNS FOR AI STRATEGY IN THE LAC REGION

The successful integration of AI into operations of a justice and security sector institutions in the LAC region requires more than a generic technology implementation plan. An effective AI strategy must be a direct and thoughtful response to the region's unique operational, social, and political challenges.¹⁵ Any roadmap for strategically acquiring and deploying AI capabilities will inevitably fall short if it does not first acknowledge and address foundational concerns that define its strategic landscape.

From earlier discussions and feedback from the EL PACCTO session in April 2025, and further informed by the analysis of the EL PACCTO 2.0 "Artificial Intelligence and Organized Crime" report,¹⁶ we can

identify five foundational concerns shaping the responsible and effective adoption of AI in the LAC justice/security sector. These concerns serve as the lens through which all subsequent decisions regarding strategic enablers—from data and talent, to compute infrastructure, and budget—can be viewed and evaluated. Figure 2 summarizes the five challenges identified, that a successful LAC-specific AI strategy should keep in mind to ensure its successful application. A generic AI strategy will be insufficient, as it is unable to overcome the challenges posed.

¹⁵ IDB (2025). *Artificial Intelligence Framework for the Inter-American Development Bank Group*. Available at: <https://publications.iadb.org/en/artificial-intelligence-framework-inter-american-development-group>

¹⁶ Cristos Velasco, Jean Garcia Periche, Juan De Dios Gómez Gómez, Miguel Bueno Benedí (2024). *Artificial Intelligence and Organized Crime*. EL PACCTO 2.0 programme. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17076986>

Figure 2 – Five concerns that a LAC-Specific AI Strategy should address to ensure its success

The first major concern raised in the report is the LAC region’s *pervasive institutional and resource fragility*, fundamentally constraining the adoption of capital-intensive technologies. Many law enforcement agencies in the region operate with limited resources and fragile institutional structures. This reality is characterized by a lack of adequate (digital) infrastructure and a scarcity of resources (from financial resources, to talent acquisition, and basic needs such as a consistent power supply), creating an uneven technological landscape where some nations advance while others are left behind. A viable AI strategy, therefore, cannot simply advocate for acquiring the most advanced tools; it must prioritize cost-effectiveness, scalability, sustainable investment, and the maximization of existing assets.

Second, the *erosion of public trust and foundational human rights risks* presents a significant barrier. In many parts of the region, public trust in state institutions is low. This deficit may be amplified strongly by AI’s “black box” effect, where opaque algorithms produce outcomes without a clear and logical explanation as their basis. As a result, the accountability and due process are at risk of being undermined. Analyses from both the EL PACCTO 2.0 programme and Fair Trials¹⁷ have issued warnings that AI deployment without robust human rights safeguards can lead to negative outcomes, including the violation of fundamental rights to privacy and a fair trial. Therefore, a core objective of any long-lasting AI strategy must be to build an environment of transparency and cooperating with the community to generate confidence among citizens.

Third, AI systems are not neutral tools; they are powerful amplifiers of *societal biases and systemic inequality*. The uncritical use of AI can reproduce, amplify, or even create new forms of (gender-based) discrimination and violence. Concrete examples from the LAC region underscore this threat. In Brazil, facial recognition technology has been shown to exhibit racially discriminatory bias against people of African descent, while in Chile similar systems have been found to institutionalize biases related to social class and skin color. Addressing these concerns involves that ethical considerations and mitigation are not treated as a secondary compliance issue, but are rather integrated into the very design of the AI strategy.

Fourth, a widespread challenge is the *fragmented governance and the lack of strategic direction*. While several LAC nations are developing broad national AI strategies, a crucial gap exists, as none of them make specific reference to how they should be addressed by the justice and security sector. This governance vacuum results in uncoordinated, ad-hoc technology acquisition, leading to uneven progress across the region and within individual countries. An effective strategy must therefore advocate for the creation of dedicated, joint AI strategies with measurable objectives specifically for justice and security authorities, providing clear guidance and preventing a patchwork of incompatible and unregulated systems.

Finally, agencies face the *asymmetric threat of criminal AI adoption*. The state’s slow, resource-limited, and regulation-bound approach to adoption of technology stands in stark contrast to the often fast-paced, unconstrained and innovative use of AI by (serious) organized crime. AI is already being used and exploited for the benefit of (serious) organized crime

¹⁷ Eliud Tapia, Luis (2024), *Artificial intelligence in public security and criminal justice systems in Latin America. Due process-based analysis*. Fair Trials. Available at: <https://www.fairtrials.org/app/uploads/2024/08/Artificial-intelligence-in-public-security-and-criminal-justice-systems-in-Latin-America.pdf>

without the need for advanced technical skills or abilities. Mexican drug cartels use AI-controlled drones and machine learning (ML) to optimize smuggling routes, while the global rise of Crime-as-a-service (CaaS) makes powerful AI attack tools accessible to a wide range of criminals. This asymmetry frames the central imperative we advocate for in this document: building a healthy, ethical, and proficient internal AI community is not merely a matter of improving efficiency, but also a defensive measure against a technologically advanced and rapidly evolving adversary.

On the positive side there are also strong advantages that the LAC region has. The widespread use of Spanish in many countries means that they can make full use of AI models' proficiency in this language, which is much better than for languages with a smaller online presence. On the flip side, since there are also many languages that are less common in the LAC region there are opportunities to collaborate on techniques to produce and use low-resource language models, as many countries will face the same challenges in this respect. There is also in many countries an opportunity to 'leapfrog' directly from outdated legacy systems to modern, AI-ready, solutions without going through intermediate technological stages. For data entry support and analytics, it is for instance easier to design a system from scratch to replace a paper-based method, than to update an unsuited legacy system with many unknown data dependencies and shadow copies. Lastly, the shared challenges with respect to organized crime have already led to strong collaborations within the LAC region. These networks can be leveraged to establish the collaborations needed for a regional AI ecosystem in the justice and security sector.

STRATEGIC ENABLERS OF AI CAPABILITY

Addressing the five foundational concerns requires a deliberate and structured approach focused on seven key strategic enablers. These enablers—compute, data, talent, ecosystems, existing domains, legislation, and budget—represent the essential building blocks for developing a mature, effective, and responsible AI capability.¹⁸

Importantly, they are not merely a technical checklist. Instead, they form an interdependent framework where each element must be strategically configured to directly counteract the challenges of institutional fragility, eroded public trust, systemic bias, fragmented governance, and the asymmetric threat of criminal AI. Since the LAC region has a large diversity in its available resources, we shall explore the enablers from both a limited resource perspective and an expansive resource perspective.

¹⁸ European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation (2024), 'AI and Policing: the Benefits and Challenges of Artificial Intelligence for Law Enforcement'. ISBN 978-92-95236-35-6 | ISSN 2600-5182 | DOI: 10.2813/0321023 | QL-01-24-000-EN-N. Available at: <https://www.europol.europa.eu/publication-events/main-reports/ai-and-policing>

COMPUTE

The computing infrastructure—encompassing hardware, IT systems, and energy supply—is the physical and digital backbone of any AI strategy. It is the foundational platform upon which all data is processed, all models are trained, and all operational applications are ultimately deployed. Consequently, the architectural decisions made for this backbone does not only affect an institution’s technical capability, but also its financial sustainability, security, and autonomy.

In a region marked by *pervasive institutional and resource fragility*, the choice of infrastructure is not a simple technical decision but a core strategic one, with profound implications for cost, security, and scalability. It dictates how an institution can affordably build its capabilities to counter the *asymmetric threat of criminal AI adoption*, where adversaries innovate without constraint. Furthermore, this

choice directly impacts the foundational challenge of *eroded public trust and risks to human rights*.

Decisions about where data is processed and stored—albeit on-premise, in a public cloud, or a hybrid model—must be made strategically to ensure legal compliance, protect data sovereignty, and build citizen confidence. The required compute power is significant for all stages of the AI lifecycle: training machine learning models, testing and validating both self-developed and externally acquired systems, and running them in practice for daily operations.

COMPUTE – RESOURCE SCENARIOS

<p>LIMITED RESOURCES</p>	<p>For an institution with a small staff and unreliable power, the strategy must be pragmatic. The focus should be on using existing computing hardware (like powerful laptops or existing servers) for applying pre-trained, open-source models that have lower computational demands. For more intensive tasks like model testing or occasional training, a pay-as-you-go public cloud model offers access to powerful resources without large upfront capital investment. Edge computing, where data is processed locally on devices like cameras, can mitigate issues with power outages and poor network connectivity while also addressing data sovereignty concerns. Energy consumption is a critical factor, and solutions must be chosen for their efficiency.</p>
<p>EXPANSIVE RESOURCES</p>	<p>A large institution with a developed tech sector can invest in dedicated, on-premise infrastructure, such as GPU clusters and High-Performance Computing (HPC) clusters, for full control over sensitive data and high-performance computing. This allows for the continuous training, testing, and deployment of large, complex AI models. Such an organization can build and maintain its own private cloud for secure operations while also using a hybrid model to leverage specialized tools from public cloud providers. Investment in modern, energy-efficient data centers with backup power solutions is crucial to ensure resilience and sustainability.</p>

DATA

Data is the single most critical enabler for any AI strategy. It includes structured records, such as case files and forensic logs, as well as a growing volume of unstructured evidence like textual reports, images from surveillance systems, audio recordings, and digital communications. When properly refined and analyzed, these data can be used to generate actionable intelligence, enhance operational efficiency, and provide strategic insight into emerging crime trends.

However, the use of data is fraught with challenges. AI systems can be powerful *amplifiers of societal biases and systemic inequality*, and the uncritical use of historical law enforcement data can reproduce, amplify or even create new forms of gender-based discrimination and violence. The garbage-in garbage-out principle strongly applies here, as AI models trained on historically biased or incomplete data will inevitably learn, replicate, and even scale those same inequities, leading to discriminatory outcomes.

A robust data strategy is therefore the primary mechanism for mitigating these risks. It must also address the *erosion of public trust* by ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability (CIA) of data through transparent governance, including storage, accessibility, and authorization protocols. In a context of *fragmented governance*, where data is often siloed, this principle underscores the need for a comprehensive framework. This begins with ensuring digitization is done properly; if historical records are converted to digital format with errors, biases, or omissions, the data is compromised from its inception. This makes establishing a framework for high-quality digitization and data federation not just a technical task, but an ethical and operational imperative.

DATA – RESOURCE SCENARIOS	
LIMITED RESOURCES	The initial focus must be on a targeted digitization effort, converting the most critical paper records into a usable digital format. What data to target first could be informed by desired AI initiatives, or by where value can be added by digitization itself rather than the focus on down-the-line usage by AI. Data quality will largely depend on manual preprocessing and cleaning by existing analysts who understand the data’s context. Data federation may be impractical; instead, data sharing will likely be ad-hoc, based on specific case requirements and facilitated by simple agreements. The institution can leverage open-source tools for basic data cataloging and quality checks.
EXPANSIVE RESOURCES	A well-resourced institution can undertake large-scale digitization projects and establish a federated database architecture to enable seamless, secure data sharing between different departments and partner agencies. It can invest in advanced data management platforms for automated data cleansing, quality control, and preprocessing (for example, applying named entity recognition (NER) to extract key information in data, such as telephone numbers, license plates and names) adhering to legal and ethical principles. A mature data governance framework would be in place, with a comprehensive data catalog and a sophisticated data lake or data warehouse to store and manage vast quantities of structured and unstructured data for analysis.

TALENT

Compute and data infrastructure alone are insufficient; an institution needs skilled personnel to extract value from these assets and build a healthy internal AI community. This human expertise is the essential bridge between raw technological potential and responsible, real-world application. These professionals are involved in the AI lifecycle, from an analyst asking the right questions to a data scientist preparing data to mitigate bias and a trained operator interpreting the results. Their work involves selecting and training appropriate models, rigorously testing outputs for accuracy and fairness, and translating complex data into actionable intelligence. This entire process ensures that technology remains a tool in service of human judgment, rather than a substitute for it.

In a region facing *pervasive resource fragility*, cultivating internal talent through upskilling current personnel might be more sustainable than relying on expensive external contractors. This investment directly addresses the *asymmetric*

threat from criminals by equipping staff to detect and combat the illicit use of AI. Furthermore, a focus on human-centric expertise, grounded in ethics and continuous learning, is the most effective way to counter the erosion of public trust. This ensures AI is used as a transparent and accountable aid to human judgment, not a replacement for it. Creating dedicated tech roles and building knowledge—even on foundational AI—can create a snowball effect, attracting new talent and providing a basis for understanding the explainability and testing of more advanced models. This talent strategy must involve the entire ecosystem, including the existing workforce, academia, and the private sector.

TALENT – RESOURCE SCENARIOS	
LIMITED RESOURCES	The focus is on upskilling the existing workforce. Personnel can be encouraged to take free or low-cost online courses offered by government partners or academic institutions. Partnerships with (local) universities can provide access to student interns who can support initial projects. The institution should start with user-friendly, open-source AI tools that do not require deep programming knowledge. A small group of motivated (tech-savvy) individuals can be trained as AI champions to drive adoption and share knowledge internally.
EXPANSIVE RESOURCES	Establish dedicated data science and AI units, actively recruiting top specialists from the private sector and academia. Formal, long-term partnerships with universities can create a steady talent pipeline and facilitate joint research projects. The institution can afford to send personnel to specialized training programs and invest in enterprise-level AI platforms that come with comprehensive vendor support and training. This creates an environment that attracts and retains high-level expertise. Appendix A of this document discusses how the Netherlands National Police attracted its talent.

ECOSYSTEM

No single institution can master the complexities of AI alone, especially when facing sophisticated, transnational criminal networks. The rapid pace of technological innovation, driven by the private and academic sectors, far exceeds the capacity of any single public entity. Consequently, building a healthy ecosystem of international and national partners is essential to keep pace with the field. This collaboration can comprise a broad scope of arrangements, ranging from short-term projects with concrete deliverables for technological, organizational, ethical, legal, and operational challenges, to the formation of long-term strategic partnerships.

This necessity for partnership is further amplified by the region’s *fragmented governance*, which often fosters uncoordinated efforts and uneven progress. An ecosystem model directly counters this by enabling agencies to pool scarce resources, share critical knowledge, and create operational synergies that would otherwise be impossible. However, such collaborations must be guided by a clear strategic agenda to ensure they contribute to a unified security posture, rather than creating new dependencies or working at cross-purposes.

ECOSYSTEM – RESOURCE SCENARIOS	
LIMITED RESOURCES	Focus on joining existing regional and international security cooperation frameworks, such as those facilitated by EL PACCTO (for example, CLASI), to gain access to shared intelligence and best practices. It can leverage programs from organizations like the Inter-American Development Bank (IDB) or UNESCO, which provide targeted support, training, and resources in the region for justice and security. ¹⁹ Collaboration will often be opportunistic, building relationships with (local) universities or non-profits for specific, small-scale projects.
EXPANSIVE RESOURCES	A well-funded institution can take a leadership role in shaping regional security ecosystems. It can initiate and fund new collaborative platforms and form strategic public-private partnerships with major technology firms to co-develop bespoke AI tools tailored to its specific needs. It can also establish and fund its own research centers or form deep, long-term partnerships with leading universities to drive cutting-edge research and create a pipeline of top-tier talent.

¹⁹ Ilan Goldfajn (2025), 'Cracking Crime with AI'. Inter-American Development Bank (IDB). Available at: <https://www.iadb.org/en/blog/cracking-crime-ai>

EXISTING DOMAINS

To maximize impact and ensure feasibility, especially in the face of *institutional and resource fragility*, an AI strategy should build upon existing institutional strengths and domains of expertise. Rather than attempting to solve every problem at once, agencies should identify specific, high-priority crime types where AI can offer a distinct advantage and where a foundation of knowledge already exists. This allows for the creation of targeted, synergistic applications of the other strategic enablers, delivering tangible wins that build momentum and justify further investment.

EXISTING DOMAINS – RESOURCE SCENARIOS	
LIMITED RESOURCES	<p>Consider, for example, that deep fakes and voice cloning are a major pre-identified concern that requires strategic AI investment. A common denominator for both is strategic development of the institution’s AI audio processing capabilities. Audio processing is a sub discipline of AI that has quite a few good open-source models which can run with limited compute (laptops could suffice). Using such models also requires limited expertise to get started. With a minor programming knowledge anyone can run, for instance, a Whisper model locally. One of the bigger challenges for a first use case such as generating transcripts for audio in digital evidence is to get the data from the main storage to the model and pushing the result back into storage. This is so it can be used to search audio via text. Once a proof-of-concept works, one wants to have a dedicated server somewhere to process batches of data. With limited resources it makes sense to first only do this for selected data that people are actively working on.</p>
EXPANSIVE RESOURCES	<p>With greater means, the approach to address the same deep fakes and voice cloning concern can be more systematic and integrated. The institution could invest in dedicated servers with powerful GPUs to run more advanced, fine-tuned audio processing and voice identification models. The data pipeline would be automated, integrating directly with the central digital evidence management system to process all incoming audio evidence in real-time, not just select files. A specialized team of AI forensic analysts would be responsible for not only managing these systems but also for validating the outputs and developing new techniques to detect sophisticated voice cloning and deepfakes. This capability would be part of a broader strategic partnership with academic and private-sector labs to stay ahead of criminal techniques. The entire process would be supported by a significant, recurring line item in the institution’s budget.</p>

LEGISLATION

The adoption of AI by the justice and security sector necessitates a parallel evolution in legal and regulatory frameworks. From an EU perspective, this approach is anchored by two key pillars: the AI Act, which regulates the technology itself, and a dual framework of data protection law that governs the data it processes. The AI Act establishes a risk-based framework that classifies most AI systems used in the justice and security sectors as ‘high-risk’. This designation imposes obligations—including robust data governance, transparency, human oversight, and accuracy—that must be met before a tool can be deployed. Before the AI Act went into effect, shared ethical principles (like the seven by the EU High-Level Expert Group on AI) guided policymakers, developers, and public agencies in shaping a common EU understanding of responsible AI development and deployment.

The Data Protection Law Enforcement Directive (LED) complements the AI Act, specifically governing the processing of personal data for law enforcement purposes. For all other activities, such

as administrative or human resources management within that same institution, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) applies. Together, these regulations ensure that all personal data is handled lawfully and proportionately, with the applicable rules depending on the specific purpose of the AI application. Although this framework establishes the essential legal basis for AI adoption, its detailed interpretation will continue to evolve through the rulings of courts in specific cases (case law) and ongoing regulatory developments.

The current reality of *fragmented governance* in the LAC region is reflected in laws that are often ill-equipped to handle the novel challenges posed by AI. A forward-looking strategy must therefore engage with the legislative process to address new crime types and consider making AI use an aggravating circumstance in sentencing, providing a direct response to the *asymmetric criminal threat*. Most importantly, new legislation is the primary tool to address the *erosion of public trust and risks to human rights*. Clear rules governing data usage, establishing transparency and accountability for how the government uses AI, are essential to prevent the violation of rights and rebuild citizen confidence.

LEGISLATION – RESOURCE SCENARIOS	
LIMITED RESOURCES	The focus could be on adapting existing legal codes to address the most pressing AI-related crimes. The institution will likely rely on legal guidance and model legislation from regional or international bodies to inform its approach. Public consultation may be limited to specific, high-impact technology deployments. The legislative process will be more reactive, responding to challenges as they emerge.
EXPANSIVE RESOURCES	An institution can work with lawmakers to proactively draft comprehensive, AI-specific legislation that anticipates future challenges. It can support the creation of specialized oversight bodies or parliamentary committees to regulate AI use in the security sector. This process would involve extensive public and expert consultation to build broad consensus and ensure the resulting laws are robust and democratically legitimate. Such a nation could take a leading role in shaping international legal norms for combating AI-driven crime.

BUDGET

An AI strategy cannot be implemented on the back of a single, one-off investment. This is especially true given the context of *pervasive institutional and resource fragility in the region*. A sustainable approach requires a sustained, long-term financial commitment that treats AI capability as an ongoing operational cost. This counters the ad-hoc technology acquisition that stems from *fragmented governance* and ensures a coherent, strategic build-up of capabilities. In addition, we advise to periodically re-evaluate budget allocations in multi-year cycles, ensuring that budget spending aligns with the current AI strategy.

Budgets must account for the entire AI lifecycle; strategically investing into AI systems themselves and the six other strategic resources. This includes budget for AI product development, procurement, and validation before its in-house application. Furthermore, *compute* and *data* budget must be allocated for, for example, R&D programs, system maintenance, digitization efforts, and

data storage. Moreover, investing into continuous *talent* development and a healthy *ecosystem* with long-term partners requires sustained financial commitments.

To maximize value, a “bang-for-buck” approach is critical. This involves strategically leveraging powerful open-source models and platforms, which can significantly reduce initial software costs, potentially augmented with commercial support contracts or “wrappers” built around open-source solutions to ensure reliability and ease-of-use. Moreover, strategically investing in talented personnel and established partnerships, as well as aligning AI investments with existing domains currently receiving funding, can help stretch funding further.

BUDGET – RESOURCE SCENARIOS	
LIMITED RESOURCES	The budget will typically be project-based, focusing on small-scale pilots with clear, measurable, and short-term objectives. The strategy will heavily rely on free and open-source software to minimize licensing costs. Funding will likely be opportunistic, pieced together from existing operational budgets and supplemented by grants from international partners or development banks. To maximize the impact of these funds, spending should be focused on pre-defined priority domains and leverage synergies within the ecosystem. For instance, a grant could fund a pilot targeting a specific crime type, developed in partnership with a local university that provides student talent and access to computational resources, thereby multiplying the value of the initial investment.
EXPANSIVE RESOURCES	The institution can allocate a significant, multi-year, dedicated budget for its comprehensive AI strategy. This could include funding for an internal R&D lab to experiment with new technologies and develop custom solutions. The budget would support a mix of internally developed systems and best-in-class commercial software for mission-critical applications, and open-source tools for flexibility, all backed by enterprise-level support contracts. This stable funding allows for long-term strategic planning and sustained capability growth.

DEPLOYING THE AI STRATEGY

Regional, national and institutional AI strategies will require cooperation along all axes of the justice and security sector. In this chapter we propose an approach for moving forward with putting strategic considerations into plans and start working on implementing those plans.

SECTORAL SPECIFICS

Within the sector there are significant differences between the AI strategy needs of institutions. A large part of this strategy roadmap focuses on investigative and law-enforcement functions since they deal with many unique challenges due to having to process raw data such as audio and video signals. However, the judicial sector has a particularly high impact when it comes to their decision making. Slow legal processes affect everyone: wrongfully accused individuals are unduly exposed to high stress and uncertainty, victims cannot find closure, limited throughput increases selectiveness of cases and leads to limited access to justice and citizens may lose trust in the legal sector. Aside from velocity, courts also must consider how to weigh evidence and conclusions that were (partly) gathered and analyzed with AI means or may have been tempered with via AI. This overlaps with other institutes that provide oversight regarding the use of AI within the justice and security sector.

The high-stakes impact of decisions by the judicial sectors makes that full automation of court decisions is often prohibited and ethically undesirable. AI efforts for the sector therefore mostly focus on the support of tasks such as document writing and search, and providing decision support rather than autonomous decision-making. As an example, the Caribbean Agency for Justice Solutions (CAJS) developed the tool JUDI (Judicial User Direct Insights) to support various task within the judiciary. Its main aim is to improve productivity by providing document generation for common tasks. CAJS also worked on AIDA – tool to support legal research. On the technical side, the judicial sector has the advantage of being mostly oriented to the text-modality. This means that it is particularly well

positioned to take advantage of the most recent developments in the field of Large Language Models.

All this to say that for an AI strategy one has to consider every institute's role. As an example; In the Netherlands the police has been much more equipped with means to develop and apply AI than the data protection authority and the inspection of the Ministry of Justice that needs to adjust in order to properly audit the police. As a consequence, a public debate among these happened through the media with respect to technologies such as facial recognition. This division does not foster trust. It is better that the sector provides a unified front and realizes that the speed of the sector as a whole is the slowest speed among its member institutes. We propose therefore to consciously build a social network of working groups across sectors, which are each responsible for various AI strategy components.

THE STRATEGIC SOCIAL NETWORK

Defining and implementing the AI strategy cannot be the work of a few individuals. A wide social network is needed to ensure that all needs, concerns and opportunities are identified and put on the agenda. Due to the cross-cutting nature of AI across the sector we propose a network of working groups (Figure 3). They could be modeled after ELSA-labs; a concept to combine societal, legal and social aspects for techno-science programmes that has its origins in the human genome project but has also been adopted for nation-wide AI development.²⁰ ELSA labs bring different stakeholders together to collaborate on research questions. For the AI strategy purposes the aim would not be research but strategic deliverables. We hence call them workgroups instead of labs.

²⁰ Van Veenstra, A.F., van Zoonen, EA., & Helberger, N. (2021), *ELSA labs for human centric innovation in AI*.

Figure 3 – Workgroup social network structure

The groups can be roughly divided in the legal domain, the domain of ethical and desirability questions and the technical domain. The legal domain would be mostly focused on the new legal frameworks that are required, the criminalization of AI and updates on for instance data protection laws. A long-term goal could be, among others, to facilitate the development of an equivalent of the EUAI act for the LAC region. The ethical domain would focus more on broader questions of what is considered desirable in society. Their broader aim would be to establish the kind of society the LAC region strives for given the impact of AI. The technical domain would be mostly concerned with important AI tools that need to be developed (such as localized foundational models) and the long-term required digital infrastructure.

For harmonization purposes it is important that these working groups overlap. For instance, though the ethics groups focus on ethics, they need input from legal and technical experts on what topics are pressing for the legal workgroup and what technology likely to be deployed in the future. Likewise, it is important that various stakeholders are represented within the working groups. This does not just include the justice and security sector, but also for instance auditors, international partners and the private sector. Depending on the size of the sector, it is likely that dedicated groups are needed within the judiciary, law-enforcement, investigative and prosecution organizations of countries.

Ideally, the various workgroups can work on strategy elements and their implementation in a decentralized manner. However, in practice it is often needed to have a core group monitor and evaluate progress, or be a single point of escalation when scarce resources have

to be divided. This core group could also help establish new working groups where they are lacking.

SETTING UP WORKGROUPS

Workgroups do not have to be completely new collaborations. In most countries there are already teams that would make for logical candidates to sprout working groups from. For instance, cybercrime teams, data protection legal teams and CSAM teams are all adjacent to AI. Also in policy-making teams and staff-layers in institutes there are usually already employees working on AI or AI related questions. It is advised that working groups are not too big and remain focused on strategic goals. Establishing these goals and reflecting on them periodically will help with staying focused.

A good connection to leadership is also important. Ultimately, many strategic discussions are related to coordinating, assigning and prioritizing scarce resources. Typically, many initiatives are launched while AI is 'hot' and then abandoned fruitlessly when long-term support could not be realized. On the other side of the coin, projects can fail and be rejected all together, where with a different approach value could have been gained. A recent MIT study exemplifies this well.²¹ The researchers found in their sample that 95% of GenAI projects let to zero return. Yet, they also note that the core issues were things like misalignment to day-to-day operations and the way that the AI was applied, rather than the performance of the AI itself. Part of those issues are up to leadership to have them addressed elsewhere, rather than at the technical side. It is also up to leadership to not spread resources over too many initiatives, in order to be able

²¹ Aditya Challapally, Chris Pease, Ramesh Raskar, Pradyumna Chari (2025), *Then GenAI Divide State of AI in Business 2025*. MIT.

Figure 4 – Sprouting working groups from existing activities.

to sustain the successful ones long-term. Similarly, legal experts often experience a lot of push back from operational teams and technical experts. Data protection is for instance often seen as a hindrance and auditors as a nuisance. For legal working groups to be successful they should have the backing of higher management.

For the inner workings of a group we propose to first follow the process of Figure 4 per group for their specific lens. This assessment process will help establish the strategic goals and initiatives to be employed. For moving forward with initiatives the group can either be a facilitator or the actual implementation party.

STRATEGIC COMPONENTS

Strategy components can be made once the main concerns and strategic means, long term goals and initial aims are established. It will be difficult to write a single AI strategy document as an AI strategy touches a lot of different areas within the sector (though an overview in a vision document would be helpful). There are many ways to slice a strategy and the list from Table 3 is a suggestion based on the experience within the EU. Typically, each component would be picked up by a different working group, with overlap between those groups. Thinking beforehand who would contribute to which components, and for whom the deliverables are, should also be informative for the participants list that is needed to make the AI strategy in the first place.

STRATEGY COMPONENTS	
VISION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Focus concerns ● End state situation
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Paper and forms, data entry ● Digital signature ● Accessibility
INTERNAL AI COMMUNITY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Community structure (SIGS, Hub and spokes, Solitary data scientists) ● HR aspects
ICT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Maintenance ● Hardware ● Long-term capabilities (buy/make, public/private)
COUNTER AI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● New specialized teams/experts
R&D	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open-source wrappers ● AI labs / academia ● Innovation
CONCEPTS AND APPLICATIONS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Model maintenance ● Platform design ● Model agnostic development
LEGITIMACY, ETHICS, TRUST	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Quality standards ● AI registry
COMMUNICATION AND EDUCATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Maintaining expertise ● Digital skills of personnel ● Understanding AI limits
COLLABORATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ecosystems of knowledge ● Closed open source

Table 3 - Suggested strategy components

VISION DEVELOPMENT

A vision is needed to maintain course on long-term transformations. At the same time, since AI is moving very fast, it is required to accept that the vision will need to be adjusted over time.

Example deliverables

A vision document that is in line with the vision for the justice and security sector as a whole, that has the support of higher management and commitment regarding its realization.

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION - SECTOR WIDE

AI works best in highly digitized environments. If processes rely on paper, physical signatures and manual actions - which is not uncommon in the legal domain - then they are not suitable for realizing AI opportunities.

Example deliverables

Transformation plan, change management strategy.

THE INTERNAL AI COMMUNITY

Most initial AI projects involve a few data scientists and some hardware. However, long term it is needed to fully specify roles, data authorizations and responsibilities and support the data scientists in their work. If the required skills are not part of curricula in schools and academia, then perhaps training programs need to be set up to bootstrap the field.

Example deliverables

HR vision, job descriptions, assigned budgets, facilitation of gatherings, a data care organization, training or coaching opportunities.

ICT

People get most excited about new AI applications, but the long-term gains can only be reached via long term support and maintenance. Often this also requires a scale up of hardware and personnel.

Example deliverables

Cloud strategy, AI architecture, buy or make strategy.

COUNTER AI

Counter AI involves adaptations that are required in the sector due to the use of AI by criminal organizations. Examples include spear phishing, autonomous turrets and autonomous delivery drones.

Example deliverables

Technology horizon scans, future scenarios, contingency plans.

RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

R&D serves various purposes. It produces the required knowledge to adapt AI techniques and methods to the specifics of the sector, it trains the future seniors that are required, it makes the sector more self-reliant, it strengthens the negotiation position with private industry, and it builds enthusiasm for working in the sector.

Example deliverables

Research programs, AI lab.

CONCEPTS AND APPLICATIONS

A development environment has to be organized that can work on concepts and applications. Concepts are about global functionalities such as summarization services and search engines for multi-

modal search. Applications are the concrete AI tools such as a summarizer of transcribed interrogations or a search engine to search through confiscated data for all mentions of an individual in text, audio and images.

Example deliverables

AI models, generic service

LEGITIMACY, ETHICS, TRUST

New ways to gather evidence or to select targets for interventions may lead to discussion in courts regarding the legitimacy of the used methods. Alongside the legal side of things, there is also a swathe of ethical risks when AI is introduced. Undesired bias is an obvious one, but others include an erosion of relevant skills among the workforce in the sector and a growing distrust of civilians if they feel that the sector is constantly spying on them on the streets and on social media. One has to prepare a strategy on how to maintain legitimacy, how to maintain the ethical standards and how to foster trust.

Example deliverables

Ethics guidelines, legal frameworks, evaluation standards, algorithm registers, ethics roundtables, awareness programs.

COMMUNICATION AND EDUCATION

Research has shown that trust in AI is not just a technical challenge but also a communicative one. For instance, the explanations that follow a decision recommendation by AI may influence how much a citizen trusts a police's AI generated advice. Additionally, to maintain support for the execution of a long-term AI strategy it is important to have regular successes to report.

Example deliverables

Media strategy, core message

COLLABORATION

Advanced AI is seldomly developed in isolation. For the justice and security sector it is however not uncommon to only have a few experts on specific topics, which makes them unique in their whole country. Examples include computer vision experts on child pornography, experts on illicit financial transaction analysis and audio experts for AI to transcribe wiretaps. For private companies it is often the case that they service multiple countries, but for internal experts they must be connected to their peers abroad. In a sense, one can view it as normal that personnel follows courses to increase their knowledge, but for these experts there are no courses. Their way to keep improving their skills is by practice and collaboration with their peers.

Example deliverables

MoU's, traineeships.

CLOSING WORDS AND NEXT STEPS

This roadmap discussed guidelines for developing a regional, national or institutional AI strategy for the Latin American and Caribbean justice and security sector. Such a strategy is needed to adequately adapt to the challenges which AI poses and to develop capabilities for using AI from within the sector. Due to the broad impact of AI and the complexity of the justice and security sector it is a daunting task for anyone to formulate a coherent overarching strategy. The guidelines are therefore tailored towards maintaining overview and focus, and dividing the task into smaller components to be solved by interdisciplinary working groups.

The next step is to move forward with establishing the first working groups. Though the EU and LAC region each face their own unique challenges, there is still much that can be learned from each other. In terms of the overall focus on legislative goals, human-centric and responsible AI, the EU and LAC region are very compatible in their way of thinking. Joint working groups on legal and technical aspects might be established based on the social network of the EL PACCTO programme. Other existing organizations such as the Caribbean Agency for Justice Solutions, the Inter-American Development Bank and the United Nations Development Programme's Digital Hub for LAC could also be explored for launching working groups.

Due to the pressing nature of AI crime it is advised that legal workgroups are organized as a top priority. The sister report "*Informe Técnico Legislativo Sobre la Tipificación Armonizada de Delitos Cometidos Mediante Sistemas y Herramientas de Inteligencia Artificial*" can be used as a starting point. For morale and momentum, it will help to have early results. The appendices contain various approaches to knowledge building, procurement and international collaboration that can help in the establishment of a technical work group. Initial exchanges can be on topics such as data analytics and computer vision models such as license plate recognition. Experience and models on these domains are proven to be valuable in practice and fairly easy to share.

Transnational serious organized crime (SOC) is a suitable core use-case among working groups. It is a shared concern that covers both negative AI consequences (such as deep fake scams, autonomous drones), institutional risks (such as using AI to process evidence and supporting court decisions), AI productivity opportunities (such as summarizing evidence) and new ways of working (such as extracting supply chains from shipping data, transactions and intercepted communication). Additionally, the transnational nature of SOC poses challenges for legal systems that calls for harmonizing legal frameworks and data exchange. These challenges can be solved on the back of the international working groups. Where possible, the work on AI that relates to SOC should be connected to (non-AI) initiatives who's focus is SOC.

All in all, AI poses many opportunities and challenges for the LAC region. There are many initiatives and resources that can be utilized to formulate and implement a long term AI strategy to support the region. Together and with partners, the region can adapt to changes that AI poses on society and work towards safer societies, efficient justice and security sectors and transnational harmonization on legal, ethical and technical AI aspects.

APPENDIX A – NATIONAL POLICE LAB AI

The Netherlands National Police has to deal with ever growing data streams that increasingly encumber its intelligence, investigation and enforcement activities in this age of digitization. The use of AI and related technology is not optional anymore. However, the widespread adoption of AI has to happen against a backdrop of public concerns regarding ethical and legal aspects of AI, unfinished and untested regulations and a state-of-the-art academic and commercial frontier with daily new developments. Faced with this challenging environment, The Netherlands National Police founded its National Police AI Lab to straddle the divide between law-enforcement practice, academia, peer governmental organizations and the (semi-)private sector. The NPAI has already proven to be an effective R&D branch that can convert academic results to improvements in the daily work of law-enforcement operatives.

The NPAI's R&D capacity is provided by its PhD students for research and its scientific programming team (TWO) for applying the research in practice. The PhD students are spread throughout the police. They either are part of operational teams or work closely with them. The members of TWO all have a background in AI or a related field. They develop applications that incorporate research results, help co-organize data science community events and act as an in-house knowledge store for concluded tracks. The benefits of having a lab include:

- A broad network of expertise to draw upon for policy choices.
- Technical solutions for niche topics within the police force.
- An overall increase in the level and quality of the police concerning AI.

- Proactive preparation for complex consequences of AI in the justice system.
- Self-reliance within the technology sector.
- Soft power at a national and international level.
- Recruitment of scarce technical expertise, and the training of our future senior staff.

RESEARCH

For its own research, the NPAI primarily relies on Utrecht University (9 PhD candidates) and TU Delft (7 PhD candidates). Additionally, there is currently 1 PhD candidate at Maastricht University. The consortia are broader and also include PhD candidates across the country. In total, the NPAI's network consists of 45 ongoing PhD projects and 10 completed projects as of late 2025. 10 of the current PhD students are internal employees who aside from their research also have regular tasks at the police.

The research projects can be divided into technical, non-technical, and combination projects. Technical topics include, for example, computer vision for surveillance and security and improved methods of intercepting fleeing subjects. Non-technical topics include the legal admissibility of evidence acquired with AI and the influence of AI within the police force on the lived experience of demonstrators. Combination projects bridge the technical and non-technical aspects. An example of this is research into transparency methods to make the support of AI in operations more understandable for analysts, detectives, and uniformed police officers.

The diversity of research constructs is necessary to maximize the impact of the research. Internal projects within, for example, the intelligence organization benefit from the researchers co-developing internally the tools that can improve the research. We see that the PhD candidates also share valuable knowledge at internal meetings such as the data science meetups, internal colloquia, and the police's data science congress. The teams where the researchers are embedded also benefit from colleagues who are additionally trained in critical thinking, scientific evaluation, and keeping up with state-of-the-art literature in their field. Furthermore, internal researchers also have a recruiting function. Several technical colleagues were once graduates at the NPAI, and approximately one-third of the PhD candidates indicate that they also want to work for the police after their PhD. The NPAI alumni network also generates a kind of soft power for the police, as alumni spread throughout defense, the AIVD (General Intelligence and Security Service), politics, and the business sector.

External research projects are often focused on the connection between the police and society. For this, it is important that academia can position itself as a 'critical friend'; that is, as a party that does not aim to only criticize the police, but independently tries to help the organization maintain legitimacy and strengthen public trust in the police. The research consortia also provide access to relevant colleagues within other organizations. For example, ALGOPOL brought together policymakers and critics on AI in government from the Public Prosecution Service (OM), the Ministry of Justice and Security (J&V), NGOs, universities, and various police units. Another example is the recently launched 'AI Compas' (Netherlands AI Compass), where the researchers form the

bridge between the police, municipalities, and academia to achieve improved crowd monitoring and control at large events.

COLLABORATION

Through the research conducted by the NPAI, the Dutch police have also been able to engage in broader collaborations within the AI world. For example, the NPAI is part of the ICAI network²², where experiences are shared about the successes and setbacks of AI in practice. The parties in that network include major companies in telecommunications, infrastructure, insurance industry, retail, and online shopping. By exchanging experiences, these parties gain a better understanding of what is truly possible and are less susceptible to misleading marketing from the technology sector.

This immediately brings us to the notion of self-reliance and sovereignty. The technology sector is dominated by a few large parties operating in various countries. For services offered to large organizations, there are not many online reviews to be found. Projects are often presented more positively on official platforms than the reality. Due to the reputation of the NPAI, several countries (including France, Austria, Norway, Scotland, UK, Belgium, Australia, and South Korea) have crossed our path, allowing us to build a more informal bond in which we exchange experiences that tell a more accurate story. These collaborations also yield AI successes, original innovative ideas, and solutions that we ourselves had not conceived. By working together as police organizations, we can improve our negotiating position and increase the self-reliance of the security sector.

²² A network within the Netherlands that connects many parties involved in AI.

APPENDIX B – INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION

Through the National Police AI Lab the French National Gendarmerie connected to the Dutch police. What started with an internship of one colleague at the NPAI ended in a collaboration agreement that focuses on practical exchange with as little as possible overhead. It was quickly agreed that data exchange, working on shared code bases and grand collaborative efforts would only introduce such overhead. Hence, the agreement is focused on a very lean approach towards collaboration. This section contains most of the text of the agreement. It is provided as a basis which may also be useful in the design of similar collaborations among LAC countries.

INTRODUCTION OF THE MOU

Law-enforcement institutes across the world explore how AI can be applied in an appropriate manner. Typical about AI is that the produced solutions' performance depends on their continuous readjustment through new data or new domain knowledge representations. Everyday decisions by law-enforcement operatives impact how well their AI can support them in their duties. Therefore, it is essential that law-enforcement institutes understand their AI systems and the users' impact on the systems' performance. Additionally, many organizations are much more comfortable with adopting AI when they have in-house expertise in AI that makes them a smart buyer. This holds both for partnerships with private parties and public parties such as universities. Most in-house expertise is cultivated through technical teams that are tied to specific operational needs. For instance, it is common in law-enforcement institutes to find AI experts who are dedicated to combating phenomena such as high-tech crime and the spread of digitized child sexual abuse material. Practice has proven, however, that expertise in such teams has a challenging time reaching other parts of the institute which may not have natural direct need for technical experts. Examples include cold-case investigators or patrol units. This is unfortunate since

most AI applications contain a generic learning and/or reasoning capability which is broadly applicable for many use-cases outside that of the specific application. For instance, a solution that can learn to recognize child abuse material can also be reapplied for learning to recognize weapons in images.

A recent development in the law-enforcement community is the founding of AI teams that provide in-house expertise but are not specifically tied to an operational use-case. Such teams tend to collaborate closely with academia and private partners to form a R&D environment for AI that explores the application of AI for a wide variety of law-enforcement use-cases and form a knowledge hub within the organization. Examples include the DataLab of the ST(SI) and the Dutch police's National Police AI Lab (NPAI).

Teams from different countries run into similar challenges and opportunities.

This has led to a call by European chief commissioners to seek collaboration among countries among the topic of AI for law-enforcement. As a result, Key Enabling Technology sessions were organized. One such session has led to an initial collaboration between the DataLab and NPAI.

MOU PURPOSE

The Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) outlines the plan to develop a partnership between the DataLab and NPAI. The aim is to expose the strategic vision of how the collaboration must take place and formalize several commitments whose goals are to solidify the partnership.

The legal aspects resulting from this partnership are precisely handled in a distinct document which details all practical modalities such as deliverable exchange, intellectual properties, and so forth.

Initial exchanges between AI's experts of both the DataLab and NPAI have proven to be very productive and can continue on several technical topics. In this context, an initial agenda, which aims to identify and detailed opportunities that can benefit from such exchanges will be authored by the DataLab and NPAI and annexed to this partnership commitment.

COLLABORATION FOCUS

Collaboration between law-enforcement institutes has proven to be challenging. There is no lack of cooperative attitude, but there is a lack of knowledge to deal with diverging regulations and ethical guidelines across institutes. Initiatives often get stranded by the lack of possibilities to share data or issues around intellectual property when one party's R&D capacity is partially delivered by private companies. Additionally, shared projects significantly increase overhead due to aspects such as doubling of the number of stakeholders to include. This has led to many talks about collaboration, but few operational results. Data sharing and co-working on shared projects can achieve important new innovations, but should be seen as a long-term endeavor.

The DataLab and NPAI aim for a collaboration with short-term gains for both parties. The collaboration described in this document therefore takes a complementary approach to data sharing and co-working. Previous collaboration between the DataLab and NPAI has shown that direct peer-to-peer connections between experts are very fruitful. The aim is to foster this type of working together through a list principled do's and don'ts. In order to avoid lengthy legal processes there will be no effort to share data, work together on projects or attempts to create joint legal frameworks. Furthermore,

technical standardization is tempting, but its realization has proven to have a low probability of success. Hence, there will also be no work on technical standardization such as data formats. Finally, both ST(SI)² and Dutch National Police always aim to minimize the time that technical experts spend in overhead meetings. An important 'don't' in this collaboration is therefore that there will be no joint events/meetings that are open to an audience who do not contribute to the R&D of AI.

Direct peer-to-peer interaction among experts has proven to be productive. The collaboration therefore specifically does include the exchange of experts and the inclusion of each other's experts when the DataLab or NPAI have an internal technical knowledge dissemination moment. For instance, both the DataLab and NPAI have an interest in combating fraud by enabling victims to effectively file online reports. Rather than jointly working on an intake system the cooperation will consist of the experts working on the AI components visiting each other physically and comparing notes, ideas and results. To further foster this exchange, both parties agree to commit to translate and provide relevant business analyses and evaluation reports. If possible, models, machine learning pipelines and reasoner software can also be exchanged. Since both parties produce in-house modules, it will often be possible to do so without complex intellectual property issues. Additionally, both parties prefer to work with open-source solutions, which naturally leads to exchange opportunities.

DO'S	DON'TS
Open-source development	Data sharing
Expert exchange	Joint legal frameworks
Project documentation translation	Shared projects
Inclusion in local dissemination	Technical standardization among partners
Model, pipeline and reasoner sharing	Overview meetings
Peer-to-peer interaction	Being a think-tank

operational issues, data-scientists can be recruited in some department, and so forth. This partnership describes a bilateral collaboration only between the DataLab and NPAI, hence it is up to this two AI lab to inform and coordinate with their own ecosystem about the collaboration's content.

GOVERNANCE

We aim to identify short term opportunities for collaboration and exchanges: the DataLab and NPAI both have their own research agenda and multi-years plans; the core idea of our partnership is to be able to determine which research topic or project could benefit from collaboration. We do not aim to produce a shared long-term agenda, since this collaboration is focused on short term gains and both labs can have different research priorities.

A shared one-year agenda will be updated every six months in order to be able to take the collaboration into account when planning resources locally: both sides also have to request resources (funds, capacity) early when they are required.

The agenda functions also as a pamphlet about the status of the collaboration. Hence, it will contain a summary of

both parties, some past activities and a summary of the future plans. Additionally, the aim is to identify one or two concrete activities for the short term.

The agenda will be authored by DataLab and NPAI directly. Two meetings per year will be dedicated to the planning process. Both sides commit to offline preparation of these meetings, i.e. sending each other project updates so that the meeting time is spent making plans. As a result of these meetings, the DataLab and NPAI will request resources as required and acknowledge that it may occur that one side is unable to procure the right resources or conditions for agreed upon joint efforts.

DataLab and NPAI will handle coordination in their own organization. The ecosystem of AI teams within law-enforcement institute is quickly evolving: new local teams can be formed to tackle specific

APPENDIX C - MAKE OR BUY

One of the strategic policies when it comes to developing the AI capabilities of the justice and security sector is the decision process regarding when AI is made or when it is procured. There are thriving open-source communities and publicly available academic resources which enable in-house development. At the same time, private vendors can specialize in the legal and security domain and thus lower costs significantly by having efficient R&D processes that earn themselves back via multiple (international) clients. A make-or-buy choice is always a compromise – which should include seriously the possibility of not going for AI at all for specific cases.

Whether AI is procured or made, there are benefits, risks and costs either way. For any individual functionality it is typical to perform a ‘make or buy analysis’. Part of those analyses is to match pros and cons of choice with strategic aims. Many countries in the LAC region share challenges and risks when it comes to procurement policies. These include limited local AI sectors, worries about sovereignty and old legacy systems. The region should therefore adopt a collaborative approach to mitigate risks and maximize benefits. In this appendix we shall discuss various strategic aspects that come into play for make or buy analyses.

PROCUREMENT RISK AND OPPORTUNITY

In general, there is likely a heavy reliance on procurement of technology for the justice and security sector in any country. Even when the choice to procure the AI is made, it still helps to have expertise on board to smartly buy the technology. It is not uncommon for government agencies to procure resources which then are not used because switching platforms or realizing system integration in legacy software turned out to be harder than expected. Similarly, technical experts can analyze the actual usage of the AI services to see where unnecessary resources are spent. For instance, the technician jobs might be not to develop and host an LLM but to minimize the token throughput.

A reliance on procurement will also create vendor dependencies and lock-ins. It is important that contingency plans are made in case access is blocked for reasons such as conflicts, the vendor going out of business, or unsustainable sharp price increases. Contingency plans should include fallback measures for such circumstances, such as non-AI solutions to get the core work done. This may involve having to foster certain skills even though in daily operations they are rarely needed.

From a strategic perspective it is also good to realize that the justice and security sector can help develop a local AI sector by providing interesting and valuable business cases. Governmental institutes can provide stable demand that is needed to grow start-ups and help educational institutes with real-world experience.

THE BASICS – AN EXAMPLE WITH SPEECH TO TEXT

For countries that already have a make or buy analysis process for non-AI software, it would make sense to not deviate too much from the current policy. However, it should be noted that AI has a few characteristics which sets it apart from other types of software. For one, AI is usually tightly connected to sensitive data. Purely from an information security perspective it might be undesired policy-wise to send data to an external party to train AI models or call them for inference. Second, knowing the purpose of the AI may already reveal capabilities that should be kept secret from an operational perspective. Third, AI often (partly) automates a task for which the proper execution is the responsibility of the appropriate authority. It would be questionable to simply outsource such tasks as it could lead to the public having the feeling that private corporations take over the judicial branch, law-enforcement or investigative institutions.

Figure 5 – Arguments for dropping, procuring or making an AI product

Aside from the aforementioned concerns, researching new technology from scratch and bringing it to practice can easily take over a decade. In addition, for AI tooling the maintenance and application of solutions will also require new specialists and hardware. The field is dynamic and within the slow-moving environment that is typical of the justice and security sector it usually is challenging to keep up with trends. Before one considers launching project to produce an end-product, it is best to start with an experiment project that is specifically designed to answer the following questions:

- Will the envisioned AI produce value?
- What are the unique qualities of the intended application that are not covered by available external solutions?
- Are development and maintenance costs at large scale feasible?

Many AI tools become obsolete quickly due to newer technology or have unclear

practical benefits due to domain specifics. For such cases it makes sense to first build a quick-and-dirty version in-house just to test it for proof of value. If value is proven, then a potential procurement can be done much more adequately by using the knowledge of the prototype. The procurement of external expertise could purely be for system integration purposes or to rebuild the solution from scratch to make it high-quality and scalable.²³

As an example, consider the use of Large Language Models and speech-to-text to support summarization and transcription of interrogations. This is an active discussion in The Netherlands at the moment of writing. On the value side the aim is to gain productivity for the following reasons:

- Currently two individuals are typically present at an interrogation due to the

²³ For instance, at the Dutch police the National Police lab AI and team pre-development regularly build AI and robotics for the sake of discovering whether procuring a tool would make sense.

burden of note-taking.

- Note-taking disrupts the conversation with the witness or suspect.
- For certain cases recordings are mandatory. These require many hours to transcribe.
- In future legislation audio-visual recordings will become more commonplace. Therefore, more recordings will have to be made and transcribed.
- Post-transcription there are still data-entry tasks such as updating records in the investigation management systems.
- Demographically speaking there will be a smaller workforce in the near future, yet a larger population. Workloads are therefore expected to increase.

The value proposition seems enticing:

- AI can transcribe the interrogation. It seems from smartphones and laptops that speech-to-text is very capable these days.
- LLMs can summarize the interrogations. Research shows that LLMs summarization tends to perform much better than earlier solutions.
- LLMs provide complementary entity extraction functionalities that support data entry.²⁴

The envisioned AI would be a solution where raw audio goes in and the various

²⁴ For example: In transcripts there are seldom properly dictated telephone numbers. The number is usually spoken with corrections and verifications interjected by speakers in the room. LLMs tend to be better in extracting the right number than pre-LLM techniques.

information products (summaries, data-entry updates, etc) come out which need to be verified by a person. To start with, experimentation was performed with open-source available models. The question of whether the AI will produce value turned out to be nuanced. There also seemed to be quite a few unique aspects of interrogations that make out-of-the-box solutions less applicable. Some observations that were made during experimentation:

- Interrogation setups have wildly different audio properties, leading to inconsistent results.
- Diarization²⁵ is not very good and costs a lot of effort to correct. Difficulties include lawyers that are phoned in via video-conference technology and people switching places within the room.
- Summarization of interrogations is a highly specialized form of summarization that is very different from summarizing news articles and books. Subtle hallucinations such as switching the tense of a sentence make LLM summaries untrustworthy at present state.²⁶
- Combing to 80+ pages of transcript to verify the correctness of AI output is still labor intensive.
- Ethnolects and dialects are inconsistently handled by the AI.
- Some users for some use-cases save many hours of labor by having an automated transcription to start from.

²⁵ Assigning in a transcript speaker identifier. Basically, annotating the transcript with who said which part.

²⁶ One example is that in a transcript the AI changed 'bloodied hand' to 'bleeding hand'.

The conclusion of these experiments is for now that making a custom speech-to-text model or LLM is unfeasible and it has to be sourced externally. However, the uniqueness of the application calls for specialized wrappers and fine-tuned models which would be possible to produce internally with the expertise that was onboarded for the experiments. In terms of value it is still considered worth further pushing the technology, even though full automation seems unlikely.

On the development and maintenance costs aspects the judgement call is made on existing AI products and the expected future of the digital infrastructure. Since there are already operational successful AI products there is a basis for converting the machines into a coherent infrastructure over the next few years. These infrastructure tasks are mostly outsourced to private partners.

The added burden of speech to text will be limited on the hardware, though larger LLMs can be significant. However, since police data cannot leave premises for legal reasons, an in-house solution must be built anyway. The open question at the moment is how feasible large scale LLM application is on in-house hardware. This will depend on developments in LLM shrinking (such as quantization) and improved methods for getting more performance out of the smaller models.

COSTS

AI projects, like any software enterprise, tend to be costly regardless of whether the choice is made to procure the AI functionality or develop it in-house. The bulk of the costs for realizing AI solutions will often lie in the non-AI aspects. Think about system integration, compliance documentation, maintenance, reskilling

and upskilling users, human oversight and formulating procedures for repairing AI mistakes. For this reason, the cost of the AI specific development, maintenance and/or licensing might only be a small component of the overall project.

From a strategic perspective, the cost of AI-specific functionalities is likely only going to be a major role for services that require constant calls to expensive models or have significant data gathering costs (including processing the data such as annotating and cleaning). If a model needs specialized hardware such as GPU clusters, then the AI-specific cost will rise quickly due to factors such as energy usage, hardware depreciation and dedicated maintenance experts. Examples would include large scale text to speech or LLM applications such as agentic AI to automate workflows. In those cases, it makes sense to consider the long term cost of licensing versus the upfront cost and maintenance of in-house solutions. For countries with ambitions for such technologies it is advisable to consider large scale in-house development or deployment only when sufficient value is highly likely given thorough experimentation in the R&D phase.

For many countries it will be impossible from an information security perspective to stream all their data to (foreign) external parties. At the same time, it should be noted that specifically for LLM applications it is unlikely that a justice or security organization will be able to host a model the size of GPT5 in a cost-effective manner. In-house LLM solutions are thus very likely to be oriented towards smaller and quantized models which perform differently. In that case 'make or buy' can be better seen from the perspective of procuring AI talent, compute cluster expertise and renting hardware versus hiring in-house experts and buying hardware.

In addition, every individual project will likely not warrant a proper digital infrastructure and thus operate on small localized solutions. Over time, this tangle of solutions is likely difficult to maintain and likely underutilizes hardware. A coherent strategy can prevent the growth of incompatible local solutions and provide a solid broad digital infrastructure which costs less in the long run due to more efficient maintenance and hardware utilization.

Many state-of-the-art AI models rely on heavy development processes for training and finetuning. Typically, this process is much more hardware intensive than applying the resulting model in practice. The development phase is often also intertwined with research practices that require scientifically schooled personnel. If there is not a sufficient business case to warrant these resources, then one could consider splitting a project into an outsourced R&D part for training/finetuning and a (potentially in-house) application part for adopting the resulting model.

IN-HOUSE TALENT

The justice and security sector is not a technology sector at its core. This means that technical experts will likely not consider working for a judicial or law-enforcement branch as one of their first choices. As a result, the required know-how for AI development might be hard to find. Having a long-term strategy for AI can help in this regard. This includes community support, career paths and a filled backlog of projects.

A steady flow of projects also helps to maintain in-house developers. If projects are few and far between then developers may opt to work for organizations where

they can apply their trade on a more consistent basis. Another common turn-off is that experts are put on tasks that are adjacent, but not quite, their expertise. An example would be machine learning experts that spend a lot of time configuring and maintaining hardware or building dashboards for data analytics, rather than training and evaluating AI models.

For legal professionals it is much more natural to already work in the justice and security sector. This segment of personnel benefits more from a long term re- and upskilling program for those that want to specialize on the legal aspects of AI.

DATA OWNERSHIP

Data that is unique to the justice and security sector is of great value and of critical importance. At all times should governments have direct access to their own data, instead of having to rely on foreign vendors. For daily operations it is possible to maintain one's own backups internally whilst working via external clouds.

Many AI projects also involve the creation of training data. This data will contain the unique specifics regarding legal terminology and law, demographics, cultural nuances and perhaps operational knowledge for countries. When procuring AI development, it is wise to include that ownership of this data enrichment also stays with the government. This will allow for switching solutions in the future.

For tasks that are not particularly bound to countries, such as license plate recognition, it is recommended to work towards shared repositories of training data. This would also require shared approaches on labelling procedures and data quality. A joint committee of experts would help

in this regard. Aside from training data it can also be considered to focus on the production of validation sets. For these sets the focus is on evaluating external tools to see how well they perform and whether that matches with claims from developers. It is of extra importance that this data remains hidden for AI suppliers, so that they cannot trick the evaluation by including this data in their training.

Data labeling or enrichment is often a menial task yet requires high levels of precision. Common examples such as recognizing general objects are typically outsourced via labelling platforms like Mechanical Turk. However, for the justice and security sector it is often required to have specialized legal or operational knowledge. Ideally, expert end-users would produce the labeling for validation and training sets. However, often their time is already under pressure, or they simply do not like the labelling task. It makes sense therefore to train a specific group of labelling personnel with the end-users. Since most tasks in the justice and security sector are likely to be text-based, it could be beneficial to have a common pool of personnel among countries that share languages like Spanish and Portuguese.

COLLABORATION

It is quite common in various sectors, such as the financial sector, to have regulatory sandboxes where products can be tested or developed. The idea is that removing compliance demands speeds up R&D without having the risk that rule-breaking systems and methods are accidentally applied in practice 'as an experiment'. The justice and security sectors of the LAC region could work towards a shared sandbox where resources such as compute are shared.

One of the challenges of becoming a smart buyer is to have trusted expertise which acts in the best interest of the sector. Similarly, for niche AI solutions such as forensic tools, it is good to have peers that can help by providing tips and feedback. It would be beneficial to have a peer to peer network among LAC countries where experts can find each other. This involves experts for all kinds of disciplines such as legal experts, procurement experts and technical experts.

For the AI that is produced in-house it is likely that for many countries the technical expertise will be scarce to find. The resulting fragility means that a loss of expertise due to illness, resignations or better opportunity elsewhere can directly threaten business processes. Risk mitigation can include proper documentation, hand-over processes and succession plans among personnel. In the international setting, LAC countries can agree to training each other's experts when suddenly key developers are unavailable and new ones need to be trained. For this to work it will be beneficial to have harmonized portfolios of AI products.

All

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